

**Permasalahan,
Kepercayaan
Umum dan Prosedur
Penggunaan
Partial Least Squares
Structural Equation
Modeling Pada
Penelitian Bisnis**

*Problems, Common
Beliefs and Procedures
on the use of Partial
Least Squares
Structural Equation
Modeling in Business
Research*

**Author:
Wawas Bangun Tegar
Sunaryo Putra**

**South Asian Journal of Social
Studies and Economics**

DOI: 10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367

Indonesian School of Research

Indonesian School of Research

South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics

Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research.

Putra, Wawas B.T.S.P

Article Information:

To cite this document:

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Permanent link to this document:

<https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Published on: 2 May 2022

Users who buy this article also get data set:

This manuscript is an Indonesian version of the original previously published paper. We also provide data sets used as illustrations of research models that you can access on <http://is-or.id/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Data-Package-Problems-Common-Beliefs-and-Procedures...-1.zip>

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

About The Author

Wawas Bangun is an Indonesian Researcher, Educational Youtuber, Trainer, Speaker and Founder of Three Promising Research Company. Wawas has spoken about SEM-PLS at several universities and has launched various types of training through the Indonesian School of Research products, namely Research Bootcamp Private Class, Research Bootcamp Group Class, and a webinar titled "Virtual Webinar on Applied Structural Equation Modeling (VWASEM)" since 2020. His passion is to teach people how to do research properly and his teaching provide people of all professional backgrounds with the theoretical and practical tools necessary to build their own research. Not only that, Wawas Bangun is an Educational Youtuber who focuses on researching educational content that has managed to get the highest number of viewers for SEM-PLS tutorial videos.

Tentang Penulis

Wawas Bangun Tegar Sunaryo Putra merupakan Founder yang sekaligus menjabat sebagai Chief Executive Officer untuk Indonesian School of Research by WRC Group. Wawas Bangun juga aktif sebagai peneliti yang secara rutin mempublikasikan artikel penelitian ilmiah dan buku, khususnya di bidang SEM-PLS. Ia telah banyak diundang untuk berbicara pada forum akademis di berbagai Universitas untuk menyampaikan materi metodologi penelitian dan statistik. Semangatnya adalah untuk mengajarkan orang-orang dari seluruh latar belakang industri maupun pendidikan agar mampu mengerti dan memahami bagaimana melakukan penelitian yang baik dan benar. Tidak hanya itu, Wawas Bangun telah sukses meluncurkan berbagai jenis pelatihan melalui produk Indonesian School of Research yaitu Research Bootcamp Private Class, Research Bootcamp Group Class, serta webinar bertajuk "Virtual Webinar on Applied Structural Equation Modeling (VWASEM)" sejak tahun 2020. Wawas Bangun juga aktif sebagai Educational Youtuber yang berfokus pada konten edukasi penelitian yang telah berhasil mendapatkan perhatian dengan jumlah penonton terbanyak untuk video tutorial SEM-PLS.

Google Scholar ID [click here](#)

ResearchGate ID [click here](#)

Orcid ID [0000-0003-2731-7895](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2731-7895)

Academia.edu ID [click here](#)

OneSearch ID [click here](#)

Garuda ID [click here](#)

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Permasalahan, Kepercayaan Umum dan Prosedur Penggunaan *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling* Pada Penelitian Bisnis

Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research

Wawas Bangun Tegar Sunaryo Putra

Indonesian School of Research, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Abstrak

Partial least squares structural equation modeling atau biasa disebut sebagai PLS-SEM dikembangkan bukan tanpa alasan. PLS-SEM dikembangkan sebagai alternatif untuk *covariance-based SEM*, yang memungkinkan peneliti untuk menjalankan penelitian *exploratory*. Selain itu, PLS-SEM dinilai mampu memberikan fleksibilitas terkait dengan karakteristik data, kompleksitas model maupun model spesifikasi. Tak ayal, PLS-SEM menjadi metode paling sering digunakan dalam banyak bidang di penelitian bisnis. Namun demikian, banyak dari peneliti yang menggunakan PLS-SEM secara tidak tepat bahkan berekspektasi lebih tanpa memahami dasar metode *structural equation modeling*. Untuk itu, artikel ini akan membahas mengenai berbagai jenis permasalahan dan kepercayaan umum atas penggunaan PLS-SEM dalam penelitian bisnis. Selain itu, artikel ini dapat dijadikan referensi untuk memudahkan peneliti terapan memutuskan metode, teknik dan alat seperti apa yang akan digunakan untuk menyelesaikan penelitiannya. Sebagai tambahan, pada bagian akhir artikel ini akan membahas mengenai bagaimana PLS-SEM dapat diterapkan untuk mengembangkan teori dalam penelitian bisnis melalui serangkaian pengantar teknis dengan mempertimbangkan kebutuhan pengguna. Artikel ini dilengkapi dengan prosedur sistematis yang membahas alur evaluasi setiap pengujian PLS-SEM melalui ilustrasi dengan model bernetasi menggunakan SmartPLS.

Kata Kunci : *Partial least squares, Structural equation modeling, Smart-PLS.*

Abstract

Partial least squares structural equation modeling (commonly referred to as PLS-SEM) was not developed without reason. PLS-SEM was developed as an alternative to covariance-based SEM, allowing researchers to conduct exploratory research. In addition, PLS-SEM is considered capable of providing flexibility related to data characteristics, model complexity, and model specifications. Undoubtedly, PLS-SEM is the most frequently used method in many fields of business research. However, many researchers use PLS-SEM incorrectly and even expect more without understanding the basic structural equation modeling method. For this reason, this article will discuss various types of problems and general beliefs about the use of

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

PLS-SEM in business research. In addition, this article can be used as a reference to make it easier for applied researchers to decide what methods, techniques, and tools will be used to complete their research. In addition, at the end of this article, we will discuss how PLS-SEM can be applied to develop theory in business research through a series of technical introductions taking into account user needs. Subsequently, this article will be equipped with a systematic procedure that discusses the evaluation flow of each PLS-SEM test through illustrations with a notated model using SmartPLS.

Keywords : *Partial least squares, Structural equation modeling, Smart-PLS.*

1. Latar Belakang Masalah

Dalam riset perilaku, terutama di bidang bisnis, ukuran sampel yang besar dan terdistribusi secara normal menjadi salah satu syarat untuk mendapatkan kumpulan data yang ideal. Namun, kenyataan yang ada dilapangan tidak mendukung hal tersebut. Banyak dari peneliti terapan yang hanya memiliki responden terbatas, hal tersebut sering terjadi karena sifat dan karakteristik dari penelitian itu sendiri. Untuk itu, para peneliti terapan sering dihadapkan pada kesulitan dalam melakukan analisis statistik atas data yang mereka miliki, terutama dalam pemodelan persamaan struktural (SEM) atas variabel laten di mana metode CB-SEM seperti LISREL (*linear structural relations*) dan AMOS (*analysis of moment structures*) memiliki asumsi kualitas data yang ketat. Untuk itu, metode PLS-SEM dirancang sebagai alternatif dari CB-SEM untuk memudahkan peneliti dalam menggunakan pendekatan SEM yang berorientasi pada model prediksi dan dinilai mampu mengurangi syarat pemenuhan asumsi kualitas data dan spesifikasi hubungan yang telah ditetapkan oleh CB-SEM (Dijkstra, 2010; Joreskog & Wold, 1982; Rigdon, 2012; Sarstedt et al., 2014).

Metode PLS-SEM pertama kali di ajukan oleh Herman Wold pada tahun 1982, metode tersebut diperkenalkan sebagai metode alternatif dari CB-SEM, bukan sebagai metode pengganti. Sejak diperkenalkannya metode tersebut, banyak bermunculan kajian-kajian yang memandang ketidaksesuaian metode PLS-SEM dalam penelitian empiris (Antonakis et al., 2010; Vandenberg, 2006; Ronkko & Evermann, 2013; Aguirre-Urreta & Marakas, 2014; Mcintosh et al., 2014; Goodhue, Lewis & Thompson, 2012; Aguirre-Urreta & Ronkko, 2018; Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020). Kajian tersebut membahas kelemahan-kelemahan yang diduga tidak dapat diatasi atas penggunaan PLS-SEM dan secara eksplisit maupun implisit menyerukan larangan dan mengutuk penggunaan PLS-SEM.

Di sisi lain, kajian yang dilakukan oleh Lohmoller (1989) serta Henseler, Hubona dan Ray (2016) menyatakan bahwa PLS-SEM masih relevan jika penelitian tersebut disertai dengan tujuan *exploratory*. Hair et al. (2017) secara spesifik menyebutkan bahwa sebuah penelitian bersifat *exploratory* ketika penelitian tersebut ditujukan untuk mencari pola dalam suatu data dengan asumsi kurang/tidak adanya teori maupun literasi sebelumnya atas variabel yang diuji, sementara sifat *confirmatory* dilakukan ketika penelitian tersebut ditujukan untuk menguji hipotesis teori dan konsep yang telah ada sebelumnya. Selain itu, alasan lain atas relevansi penggunaan metode PLS-SEM adalah adanya dugaan atas kesalahan spesifikasi model

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

pengukuran pada penelitian sebelumnya. Kesalahan tersebut dapat diidentifikasi jika peneliti tidak yakin atas efek kausal atau hubungan antara konstruksi eksogen dan endogen yang akan mereka uji (Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020). Untuk itu, PLS-SEM lebih tepat digunakan untuk memprediksi daripada mengestimasi hubungan antar variabel laten atau konstruk dalam model yang telah dihipotesiskan.

Meskipun sejak awal PLS-SEM telah dikenal sebagai metode untuk penelitian yang memiliki tujuan *exploratory*, beberapa penelitian menjelaskan bahwa PLS-SEM dapat digunakan untuk tujuan *confirmatory* maupun *exploratory* (Ringle et al., 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2016; Schubert, Henseler, & Dijkstra, 2018). Pada saat bersamaan, metode PLS-SEM tampaknya diterima di banyak jurnal atau publikasi untuk tujuan *confirmatory* karena menggunakan dukungan teori yang kuat untuk pengujian (Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020). Kondisi tersebut mengantarkan para ahli metodologi statistik kepada perdebatan atas penggunaan PLS-SEM yang tak berujung, serta membuat para peneliti terapan menghiraukan kajian-kajian atas kelemahan penggunaan PLS-SEM sehingga mereka memakai metode tersebut dalam semua jenis situasi dan berbagai macam tujuan penelitian.

Artikel ini akan membahas beberapa permasalahan yang sering muncul atas penggunaan metode PLS-SEM yang tidak tepat dan berlebihan, serta mengembalikan prinsip-prinsip dasar PLS-SEM ke dalam *structural equation modeling*. Peneliti terapan perlu memahami adanya situasi dan kondisi yang tepat atas penggunaan PLS-SEM maupun CB-SEM ketika melakukan analisis data. Dengan kata lain, ada kalanya mereka harus memahami kenapa PLS-SEM dapat/tidak dapat diterapkan dalam penelitian manajemen, sehingga menghindari adanya keputusan bahwa PLS-SEM dapat digunakan sebagai metode pilihan utama di berbagai domain. Peneliti terapan memang sering kali menemukan dirinya pada keletihan, ketika mereka diharuskan untuk memutuskan menggunakan pendekatan metode CB-SEM. Keletihan tersebut dikarenakan adanya keharusan untuk memahami penggunaan CB-SEM yang membutuhkan asumsi statistik yang jauh lebih kompleks dan rumit. Dampak dari hal tersebut, peneliti terapan selalu menganggap bahwa PLS-SEM merupakan metode andalan karena tidak membutuhkan upaya untuk memahami dasar-dasar statistik (Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020). Sebenarnya, hasil temuan dari publikasi yang masih bersikeras menggunakan PLS-SEM untuk tujuan *confirmatory* patut untuk dipertanyakan, karena hal tersebut bertolak belakang dengan tujuan awal PLS-SEM yang secara alami dikembangkan untuk tujuan *eksploratory*. Akibatnya, dapat dipastikan bahwa keputusan untuk menggunakan PLS-SEM merupakan keputusan yang tidak tepat ketika penelitian tersebut memiliki tujuan *confirmatory*, karena sebagian besar temuan sebelumnya tidak memenuhi kemajuan dinamika saat ini (Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020).

Selain permasalahan diatas, banyak penelitian terapan yang masih menggunakan prosedur yang tidak tepat ketika mereka menjalankan metode PLS-SEM. Untuk itu, artikel ini akan mengidentifikasi dan melakukan kajian atas kesalahan-kesalahan umum yang sering dilakukan dengan membandingkan pendapat dari berbagai ahli metodologi statistik dari berbagai sumber literasi. Selanjutnya, artikel ini akan menyajikan alur sistematis untuk mengevaluasi pengujian

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

pada metode PLS-SEM, dimana, alur tersebut akan disajikan menggunakan contoh bernotasi dengan aplikasi SmartPLS. Kajian dalam artikel ini diharapkan dapat menjadi acuan bagi peneliti terapan dalam mengadopsi metode PLS-SEM, serta membantu mereka untuk memutuskan metode mana yang layak untuk mereka gunakan.

2. Kajian Teori

Peneliti terapan di bidang ilmu sosial telah mengenal alat analisis statistik sejak beberapa dekade yang lalu. Dari mulai penggunaan analisis univariat dan bivariat untuk memahami data dan hubungan antar variabel. Namun seiring transformasi yang terjadi pada penelitian sosial, peneliti mulai dihadapkan pada model penelitian yang cukup kompleks karena adanya kemajuan dinamika bisnis saat ini. Untuk itu, dalam memahami hubungan yang lebih kompleks terkait dengan arah penelitian saat ini, peneliti memerlukan metode analisis data multivariat yang lebih canggih. Analisis multivariat merupakan metode statistik yang secara bersamaan mampu menganalisis banyak variabel, mulai dari penggunaan teknik generasi pertama yaitu *cluster analysis*, *exploratory factor analysis*, *multidimensional scaling* dan berkembang menjadi generasi kedua yaitu PLS-SEM. Di sisi lain, dalam hal ini penelitian *confirmatory*, teknik generasi pertama di mulai dari penggunaan *analysis of variance*, *logistic regression*, *multiple regression*, *confirmatory factor analysis* dan berkembang menjadi CB-SEM (Hair et al., 2017).

Structural equation modeling (SEM) memungkinkan peneliti untuk menguji rangkaian hubungan yang kompleks dan rumit. Dimana kondisi tersebut tidak mampu dilakukan jika menggunakan teknik analisis sebelumnya. Dalam analisis SEM, terbagi menjadi dua jenis yaitu SEM berbasis kovarians (CB-SEM) dan SEM berbasis *partial least square* (PLS-SEM). Menurut Hair et al. (2017), CB-SEM digunakan untuk mengkonfirmasi (atau menolak) teori maupun hubungan hipotesis yang telah ada sebelumnya. Hal tersebut dilakukan dengan menentukan seberapa baik model teoretis yang diusulkan dapat memperkirakan matriks kovarians untuk kumpulan data sampel. Sebaliknya, PLS-SEM digunakan untuk mengembangkan teori dalam penelitian eksplorasi yang mungkin belum pernah ada sebelumnya. Hal tersebut dilakukan dengan berfokus pada menjelaskan varians dalam variabel dependen ketika memeriksa model.

3. Kajian Temuan Masalah

Permasalahan Pertama : Ketidaksesuaian Penggunaan PLS-SEM

Seorang ilmuwan bernama Herman Wold, pertama kali memperkenalkan metode PLS-SEM pada tahun 1982. Metode tersebut merupakan jawaban dari masalah yang timbul atas penggunaan metode CB-SEM, masalah yang timbul diantaranya adalah kurangnya fleksibilitas terkait dengan karakteristik data, semakin berkembangnya model penelitian yang memiliki kompleksitas tinggi dan lain sebagainya. Pada awalnya, PLS-SEM diperkenalkan sebagai alternatif dari CB-SEM yang mengadopsi metode *composite factor* untuk menghasilkan estimasi parameter dari kombinasi linier atas variabel teramati dari sebuah konstruk laten. Hal tersebut menjadi pembeda dengan metode pendahulunya yaitu, CB-SEM, dimana metode yang

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

digunakan adalah *common factor*. Untuk itu, banyak sekali perbedaan yang ditemukan dari kedua metode tersebut (penjelasan selengkapnya terdapat pada Tabel 1).

Tabel 1.

Perbedaan antara Composite Factor (PLS-SEM) dan Common Factor (CB-SEM)

<i>Composite Factor Method</i>	<i>Common Factor</i>
<i>Partial Least Squares Path Modeling (PLS-PM)</i>	<i>Maximum Likelihood-based CBSEM (ML-CBSEM)</i>
<i>Generalized Structure Component Analysis (GSCA)</i>	<i>Diagonal Weighted Least Squares (DWLS-CBSEM)</i>
<i>Consistent PLS (PLSc)</i>	<i>Weighted Least Squares Maximum Variance (WLSMV-CBSEM)</i>
<i>Weighted PLS</i>	<i>Asymptotic Distribution Free (ADF-CBSEM)</i>
<i>PLS Predict</i>	<i>Generalized Least Squares (GLS-CBSEM)</i>
<i>Statistical Software</i>	
SmartPLS	AMOS
Warp PLS	LISREL
PLS Graph	MPLUS

Sumber : Afthanorhan, Awang dan Aimran (2020)

Composite-based structural equation modeling diketahui memiliki tiga pendekatan yaitu (1) *regression on sum scales*, (2) *generalized structured component analysis*, dan (3) *PLS analysis*. Ketiga pendekatan tersebut menggunakan estimasi *ordinary least square*, yang bertujuan untuk mendapatkan koefisien jalur dan pemuatan indikator dengan bantuan algoritma iteratif untuk meminimalkan fungsi kriteria. Dari semua pendekatan tersebut, hanya *PLS analysis* yang menggunakan dua langkah yang disebut estimasi model pengukuran dan model struktural (Hwang, Takane & Tenenhaus, 2015; Ronkko, McIntosh & Antonakis, 2015; Ronkko et al., 2016). Beberapa peneliti menyakini bahwa *composite-based* merupakan satu-satunya alasan untuk tujuan eksplorasi karena PLS-SEM (*composite factor*) memperkirakan model yang lebih umum daripada CBSEM dan kurang mempertimbangkan kesalahan spesifikasi model atau adanya model yang buruk pada beberapa bagian model. Pada dasarnya, estimasi yang diperoleh tidak ada artinya jika model *common factor* tidak diterima, dan dengan demikian *common factor* selalu dipandang sebagai alat *confirmatory* (Antonakis et al., 2010; Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020).

Namun demikian, banyak dari peneliti mengungkapkan bahwa keputusan mereka untuk memilih PLS-SEM didasarkan pada kepercayaan bahwa PLS-SEM mampu digunakan baik untuk *confirmatory* dan *exploratory*. Hair et al. (2017) menjelaskan perbedaan antar keduanya, dimana dijelaskan bahwa sebuah penelitian bersifat *exploratory* ketika penelitian tersebut memiliki tujuan untuk mencari pola dalam suatu data dengan asumsi kurang/tidak adanya teori maupun literasi sebelumnya atas variabel yang diuji, sementara sifat *confirmatory* dilakukan

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

ketika penelitian tersebut ditujukan untuk menguji hipotesis teori dan konsep yang telah ada sebelumnya. Singkatnya, jika penelitian ditujukan untuk mengembangkan teori, maka penelitian tersebut merupakan penelitian *exploratory*. Sebaliknya ketika penelitian tersebut ditujukan untuk menguji ulang konsep yang telah ada, maka penelitian tersebut merupakan penelitian *confirmatory*. Namun demikian, perbedaan antara penelitian *exploratory* dan *confirmatory* tidak sejelas yang didefinisikan, banyak sekali kriteria tujuan yang menyertainya.

Tabel 2.

Perbedaan antara Confirmatory dan Exploratory

CONFIRMATORY	EXPLORATORY
Menguji kembali teori yang telah ada kedalam domain/studi kasus yang lain Mengkonfirmasi hubungan variabel yang telah ada	Mengembangkan model baru berdasarkan kurangnya bukti atau fakta lapangan Menghubungkan ide/logika untuk memahami hubungan sebab-akibat
Bertujuan untuk mengestimasi Hasil yang didapatkan akan signifikan secara statistik Hasil yang didapatkan merupakan jawaban pasti untuk hipotesis	Bertujuan untuk memprediksi Hasil yang didapatkan hanya merupakan hubungan potensial Hasil yang didapatkan untuk menjawab novelty
Bertujuan untuk menguji teori Menguji hipotesis penelitian Menghasilkan akurasi yang tinggi	Bertujuan untuk mengembangkan teori
Menguji hipotesa yang telah diuji sebelumnya Memaksimalkan kepercayaan atas hasil yang ditemukan Menggunakan pendekatan <i>common factor</i> Memodifikasi teori yang ada dengan memasukkan jalur atau konstruksi baru	Membangun kemungkinan adanya korelasi hubungan antar variabel Merancang eksperimen yang efisien Memperkuat kesimpulan yang dikonfirmasi Menggunakan pendekatan <i>composite factor</i> Sepenuhnya mengubah item pengukuran dalam teori yang ada
Mengintegrasikan dua atau lebih teori	Mengubah hubungan antar konstruk dari teori sebelumnya (seperti menguji hubungan timbal balik)
Cocok digunakan untuk konstruk perilaku (seperti <i>Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty, Trust, Distrust, Attitudinal, Communication, Affective, Emotion, Leadership, Performance</i>)	Cocok digunakan untuk desain konstruk (seperti <i>Brand equity, Type of system, Information source, Decision-making perspective, Network structure, Network capability, Technology, Device, Location</i>)
Direkomendasikan CB-SEM	Direkomendasikan PLS-SEM

Sumber : Afthanorhan, Awang dan Aimran (2020)

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Untuk itu, peneliti perlu memahami bahwa kedua tujuan penelitian tersebut (lihat tabel 2), baik *confirmatory* maupun *exploratory* memiliki tujuan serta teknik yang berbeda, tidak hanya itu, adanya perbedaan kriteria yang harus dipenuhi menjadi salah satu alasan untuk peneliti harus memahami kondisi dan situasi yang akan membawa mereka kedalam keputusan penggunaan CB-SEM ataupun PLS-SEM. Faktanya, ketika peneliti mengambil keputusan yang tidak sejalan antara tujuan dan metode penelitiannya, konsekuensinya adalah hasil penelitian yang tidak dapat dipertanggung jawabkan (Ioannidis, 2005). Dimana hasil yang tidak tepat dapat menyebabkan kesimpulan yang akan berdampak pada keputusan yang akan diambil oleh manajerial. Dalam penelitian bisnis, sesuatu yang diukur kadang bersifat abstrak, itu dapat terjadi karena adanya berbagai macam perspektif yang berbeda muncul ketika peneliti ingin melakukan proyek penelitiannya. Situasi dan kondisi yang seperti ini dapat menjadi buruk dalam banyak hal, seperti adanya logika yang salah, desain yang tidak tepat, sampai dengan kesalahan penggunaan metode statistik (Wagenmakers et al., 2012). Henseler (2017) berpendapat bahwa karakteristik konstruk laten dapat menentukan karakter desain penelitian. Oleh karena itu, setiap faktor yang menggambarkan konstruk perilaku harus diperiksa dengan CBSEM (metode *confirmatory*), sedangkan desain-konstruk harus diuji dengan PLS-SEM (metode *exploratory*).

Permasalahan Kedua : Ketidaktepatan Penggunaan Uji *Goodness of Fit* (GoF)

Seperti yang telah disampaikan sebelumnya, PLS-SEM dikembangkan dengan tujuan untuk metode prediktif. Namun demikian, para ahli metodologi masih berusaha untuk mengembangkan metode PLS-SEM agar dapat digunakan untuk menguji teori. Upaya tersebut terlihat dari adanya pengembangan kriteria kelayakan model dari waktu ke waktu. Indeks kecocokan model memungkinkan menilai seberapa baik struktur model yang dihipotesiskan sesuai dengan data empiris dan, dengan demikian, membantu mengidentifikasi kesalahan spesifikasi model (Hair et al., 2017). Awal pengajuan kriteria model dalam PLS-SEM diajukan oleh Tenenhaus et al. (2004) dan Tenenhaus et al. (2005), mereka mengajukan kriteria GOF yang merupakan ukuran tunggal yang digunakan untuk memvalidasi performa gabungan antara model pengukuran (*outer model*) dan model struktural (*inner model*). Nilai GoF index ini diperoleh dari *averages communalities index* dan R^2 model rumus statistik sebagai berikut $GoF = \sqrt{Com \times R^2}$. Tenenhaus et al. (2004) mengusulkan indeks *goodness-of-fit* (GoF) sebagai solusi untuk memvalidasi model PLS secara global (Tenenhaus et al., 2004).

Namun Henseler dan Sarstedt (2013) melakukan uji coba pada indeks yang diajukan oleh Tenenhaus et al. (2004) pada dua model termasuk model konseptual dan model empiris. Hasil dari uji coba yang dilakukan menyimpulkan bahwa GOF tidak mampu merepresentasikan kriteria *goodness-of-fit* pada PLS-SEM (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013; Hair et al., 2017). Sebagai tambahan, GoF, tidak seperti ukuran kecocokan di CB-SEM, kriteria tersebut tidak dapat memisahkan model yang valid dari yang tidak valid. Karena GoF juga tidak berlaku untuk model yang diukur secara formatif dan tidak mampu memenuhi upaya overparametrisasi,

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

peneliti terapan disarankan untuk tidak menggunakan kriteria GoF yang diajukan oleh Tenenhaus et al. (2004).

Tahap pengembangan kriteria kelayakan model dilanjutkan oleh Henseler et al. (2014) yang menilai kesesuaian kriteria *standar root mean square residual* (SRMR) yang merupakan indeks kecocokan yang diadopsi dari metode CB-SEM. SRMR didefinisikan sebagai perbedaan akar rata-rata kuadrat antara korelasi yang diamati dan korelasi model-tersembunyi. Indeks SRMR merupakan ukuran kecocokan mutlak, dimana nilai nol menunjukkan kecocokan sempurna. Pada metode CB-SEM, nilai kurang dari 0.08 umumnya dianggap cocok (Hu & Bentler, 1998). Tetapi ambang batas ini kemungkinan terlalu rendah untuk PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2017). Pernyataan tersebut bukan tanpa alasan, perbedaan yang terjadi antara korelasi yang diamati dan korelasi model-tersembunyi memainkan peran yang berbeda dalam CB-SEM dan PLS-SEM. Algoritma CB-SEM bertujuan untuk meminimalkan perbedaan, dalam PLS-SEM, perbedaan dihasilkan dari estimasi model, yang bertujuan untuk memaksimalkan varians yang dijelaskan dari konstruk endogen.

Selain kriteria SRMR, sebagai ukuran kecocokan model alternatif, peneliti dapat menggunakan *root mean square residual covariance* (RMS_{θ}), yang menggunakan logika yang sama dengan SRMR namun bergantung pada kovarians. Kriteria tersebut diperkenalkan oleh Lohmöller (1989) tetapi belum banyak dilakukan eksplorasi percobaan oleh peneliti PLS-SEM. Hasil percobaan awal menunjukkan nilai ambang (konservatif) untuk RMS_{θ} sebesar 0.12. Artinya, nilai RMS_{θ} di bawah 0.12 menunjukkan model yang cocok, sedangkan nilai yang lebih tinggi menunjukkan kurang cocok (Henseler et al., 2014). Terakhir, Dijkstra dan Henseler (2015b) memperkenalkan *exact fit test*. Uji berbasis chi-kuadrat tersebut menerapkan prosedur *bootstrapping* untuk mendapatkan nilai p dari perbedaan antara korelasi yang diamati dan korelasi yang diimplikasikan oleh model. Berbeda dengan SRMR, ketidaksesuaian tidak dinyatakan dalam bentuk residual tetapi dalam bentuk jarak, yang dihitung dalam dua bentuk (*Euclidean and geodesic distance*). Hasil percobaan awal menunjukkan bahwa SRMR, RMS_{θ} dan *Exact Fit Test* mampu mengidentifikasi berbagai kesalahan spesifikasi model (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015a; Henseler et al., 2014). Namun demikian, penggunaan model fit tersebut masih terlalu awal dan hanya terdapat sedikit literasi yang diketahui mengenai bagaimana kriteria pengukuran ini dapat diterima untuk berbagai data dan konstelasi model, sehingga diperlukan lebih banyak penelitian lagi yang dapat mengeksplorasi kriteria-kriteria yang lain. Selain itu, kriteria ini tidak dapat secara mudah diimplementasikan dalam perangkat lunak PLS-SEM standar. Namun, SmartPLS menyediakan ukuran SRMR, RMS_{θ} dan *exact fit test* (Hair et al., 2017).

Lalu, apakah PLS-SEM benar-benar tidak dapat menjalankan penelitian *confirmatory*? Beberapa peneliti (Ringle et al., 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2016; Schuberth, Henseler, & Dijkstra, 2018) sepakat bahwa, PLS-SEM dapat digunakan untuk penelitian *confirmatory* seiring dengan dimulainya eksplorasi pengembangan kriteria kelayakan model. Namun, ketiga kriteria kelayakan di atas harus terpenuhi seiring dengan digunakannya metode PLS-SEM untuk tujuan *confirmatory*.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Permasalahan Ketiga : Kriteria Penilaian Signifikansi *Loadings* Yang Masih Lemah

Banyak dari peneliti terapan beralih dari CB-SEM ke PLS-SEM, hanya karena menemukan nilai *loadings* yang ditemukan lebih besar dari CB-SEM (Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020). Namun disisi lain, masih ada perbedaan pendapat atas kriteria batas penilaian untuk nilai indikator *loadings*. Menurut Hair et al. (2017) nilai signifikan *outer loadings* masih sangat lemah, sehingga aturan umum yang ditentukan untuk batas nilai *outer loadings* adalah diatas 0.708. Namun demikian, peneliti terapan di bidang ilmu sosial sering menemukan nilai *loadings* dibawah 0.70, terutama pada saat mereka menjalankan penelitian *exploratory*. Untuk itu, peneliti disarankan untuk menyimpan item dengan muatan nilai *loadings* antara 0.4 sampai 0.7 selama nilai *internal consistency reliability* (dalam hal ini *Average Variance Extracted*, *Composite Reliability*, dsb) telah memenuhi syarat pengujian. Untuk itu, keputusan dalam mengambil batas nilai dari *loadings* harus mempertimbangkan banyak faktor dan/atau kondisi, baik dari tujuan penelitian (*exploratory* atau *confirmatory*) maupun kondisi dari nilai *internal consistency reliability* itu sendiri. Sebagai catatan tambahan, penelitian yang dilakukan oleh Afthanorhan, Awang dan Aimran (2020) menunjukkan adanya kondisi dimana validitas dan reliabilitas sebuah konstruk sangat sensitif dan bergantung pada banyaknya jumlah item per konstruk dan nilai dari *loadings* itu sendiri, semakin tinggi nilai *loadings*, maka semakin tinggi pula nilai AVE dan CR.

Permasalahan Keempat : Adanya Perdebatan Atas Penggunaan Fornell Larcker Criterion Untuk Menguji *Discriminant Validity*

Discriminant validity digunakan untuk melihat sejauh mana suatu konstruk benar-benar berbeda dari konstruk lain dengan menggunakan standar empiris. Dengan demikian, menguji *discriminant validity* dapat membantu peneliti untuk dapat melihat apakah sebuah konstruk berbeda dengan konstruk yang lain, serta menangkap fenomena yang mungkin tidak diwakili oleh konstruk lain dalam model. Secara tradisional, para peneliti mengandalkan dua ukuran validitas diskriminan. *Cross-loading* biasanya merupakan pendekatan pertama untuk menilai validitas diskriminan dari indikator. Kriteria selanjutnya adalah Fornell-Larcker, dimana pendekatan tersebut memiliki tujuan untuk menilai validitas diskriminan dengan membandingkan akar kuadrat dari nilai AVE dengan korelasi variabel laten (Hair et al., 2017). Namun Henseler et al. (2015) menyarankan untuk menggunakan HTMT sebagai pengganti *fornell larcker criterion*. Hal tersebut dilandaskan pada kegagalan percobaan pengujian *fornell larcker criterion* untuk mengidentifikasi validitas diskriminan pada kasus besar. Pengujian *fornell larcker criterion* dilakukan dengan membandingkan akar kuadrat dari AVE untuk setiap konstruk dengan nilai korelasi antar konstuk dalam model (Hair et al., 2017). Suatu konstruk dinyatakan valid jika mempunyai korelasi akar kuadrat AVE tertinggi dengan konstruk yang dituju dibandingkan akar kuadrat AVE dengan konstruk lain. Salah satu alternatif dari pengujian *fornell larcker criterion* adalah *heterotrait monotrait ratio of correlations* (HTMT).

Namun demikian, ambang batas nilai dari HTMT masih diperdebatkan (Hair et al., 2017). Penelitian yang dilakukan oleh Henseler et al. (2015) menyarankan nilai ambang batas 0.90

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

jika model jalur memiliki konstruksi yang secara konseptual sangat mirip. Namun, ketika konstruk dalam model jalur secara konseptual jauh berbeda, nilai ambang batas yang lebih rendah yaitu 0.85 sangat disarankan (Henseler et al., 2015; Hair et al., 2017). Untuk itu, peneliti disarankan untuk melihat HTMT_{inference} melalui prosedur *bootstrapping* dengan nilai *confidence interval*. Sebagai langkah awal untuk menjalankan pengujian HTMT_{inference}, prosedur *bootstrapping* dengan subsampel 5000 dijalankan untuk mendapatkan nilai *confidence interval*. Melalui prosedur *bootstrapping*, subsampel diambil secara acak (dengan penggantian) dari kumpulan data asli (Hair et al., 2017). Kemudian subsampel tersebut digunakan untuk mengestimasi model, dimana proses tersebut dilakukan secara berulang sampai jumlah yang ditentukan, penentuan subsampel disarankan sebesar 5.000. Parameter yang diestimasi dari subsampel (dalam hal ini, statistik HTMT) digunakan untuk mendapatkan galat standar untuk estimasi.

Penelitian yang dilakukan oleh Henseler et al. (2015) secara kritis menguji kriteria *cross-loading* dan kriteria Fornell-Larcker untuk penilaian validitas diskriminan. Penelitian tersebut telah menemukan bahwa kedua pendekatan tersebut tidak dapat mendeteksi masalah validitas diskriminan secara akurat. Mereka mengungkap bahwa *cross-loading* gagal untuk menunjukkan kurangnya validitas diskriminan ketika dua konstruksi berkorelasi sempurna, dimana kondisi tersebut membuat kriteria ini tidak efektif untuk penelitian empiris. Demikian pula, kriteria Fornell-Larcker berkinerja sangat buruk, terutama ketika pemuatan indikator dari konstruksi yang dipertimbangkan hanya sedikit berbeda. Ketika pemuatan indikator bervariasi lebih kuat, kinerja kriteria Fornell-Larcker dalam mendeteksi masalah validitas diskriminan meningkat tetapi secara keseluruhan masih cenderung buruk. Sebagai kesimpulan dari perdebatan diatas, peneliti terapan disarankan untuk dapat mengambil keputusan dengan mempertimbangkan situasi dan kondisi yang ada, yang telah dijelaskan sebelumnya.

Kepercayaan Umum Pertama: Pemilihan PLS-SEM Didasarkan Pada Jumlah Sampel Yang Kecil

PLS-SEM telah dikenal sebagai salah satu metode yang menawarkan kemampuan pengambilan sampel khusus yang tidak dimiliki alat analisis *multivariate* lainnya. Namun hal tersebut dibantah oleh Sarstedt et al. (2017) yang menyatakan bahwa memang PLS-SEM dapat diterapkan dengan sampel yang lebih kecil pada banyak kasus, namun legitimasi analisis tersebut tergantung pada ukuran dan sifat populasi (misalnya, dalam hal heterogenitasnya). Tidak ada metode statistik (termasuk PLS-SEM) yang dapat mengimbangi sampel yang dirancang dengan buruk (Sarstedt et al., 2017).

Keputusan penggunaan PLS-SEM yang hanya didasarkan pada tersedianya sampel yang kecil tidak diperbolehkan, hal tersebut dikarenakan metode estimasi yang dikembangkan oleh PLS-SEM tidak menyelesaikan masalah sampel. Jika kita kembali pada metodologi dasar, pengambilan sampel populasi merupakan proses memilih sebagian kelompok subjek atau responden yang mewakili keseluruhan populasi (Polkinghorne, 2005). Ukuran estimasi sampel yang diperoleh berdasarkan pengambil dari populasi harus direfleksikan dengan populasi yang sebenarnya untuk memastikan estimasi yang sebenarnya dapat menjawab pertanyaan

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

penelitian. Untuk memastikan kelayakan estimasi tersebut, ukuran sampel yang cukup diperlukan untuk metodologi statistik yang melibatkan pendekatan model persamaan struktural (Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran, 2020). Untuk itu Hair et al. (2017) menyarankan untuk menggunakan beberapa perhitungan sampel seperti melipat gandakan sampel lima sampai sepuluh kali jumlah indikator teramati. Namun, ketika peneliti di hadapkan pada jumlah sampel yang terbatas/kecil, peneliti diharuskan untuk melihat kriteria batasan signifikansi *loadings* sesuai dengan jumlah sampel yang dimiliki (lihat Tabel 3).

Tabel 3.

*Kriteria Signifikansi Loadings
berdasarkan Ukuran Sampel*

<i>Sample Size</i>	<i>Loadings</i>
50	0.75
60	0.70
70	0.65
85	0.60
100	0.55
120	0.50
150	0.45
200	0.40
250	0.35
300	0.30

Sumber : Hair et al. (2020)

Kepercayaan Umum Kedua: SEM-PLS Dapat Mengevaluasi Uji Secara Simultan

Seperti yang di jelaskan pada bab sebelumnya bahwa PLS-SEM merupakan alternatif dari CB-SEM yang memiliki teknik estimasi parameter yang berbeda. Namun, beberapa hal perlu di perjelas dalam kaitannya dengan tujuan dari penelitian yang sedang dijalankan. Beberapa peneliti terapan masih memiliki ekspektasi bahwa PLS-SEM mampu menjalankan hubungan secara simultan. Berbeda dari CB-SEM yang berbasis pada *common factor*, algoritma PLS-SEM tidak secara bersamaan menghitung semua hubungan model secara bersama-sama (simultan) melainkan menggunakan *ordinary least squares regressions* untuk memperkirakan hubungan regresi model secara parsial – hal tersebut dapat diungkapkan dari namanya yaitu *partial least square* (Sarstedt, Ringle & Hair, 2017). PLS-SEM menerapkan *ordinary least squares regressions* (OLS) dengan tujuan meminimalkan adanya varians residual dari konstruksi endogen. Untuk itu, PLS-SEM dapat memperkirakan koefisien dari hubungan model jalur yang memaksimalkan nilai R^2 dari konstruksi endogen. Oleh karena itu PLS-SEM adalah metode yang direkomendasikan untuk tujuan penelitian *exploratory*, sehingga PLS-SEM dianggap sebagai pendekatan berbasis varians untuk SEM.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

4. Prosedur/Tahapan Spesifikasi Model PLS-SEM

Dalam upaya memahami bagaimana metode PLS-SEM dapat diterapkan pada penelitian eksploratori, penulis melakukan penelitian dengan menggunakan model uji coba untuk memahami pengaruh dari Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) dalam meningkatkan SME's Innovation Performance (IP) melalui Organizational Commitment (OC) sebagai variabel mediasi. Secara keseluruhan, penelitian ini mendapatkan sebanyak 170 responden yang merupakan pemilik usaha dan senior executives dari UMKM sektor retail yang berada di wilayah DKI Jakarta. Sebagai salah satu upaya dalam melakukan penyebaran kuesioner, peneliti memberikan beberapa pertanyaan saringan yang berkaitan dengan peran responden dalam bisnis UMKM dimana mereka bekerja. Hal tersebut dilakukan untuk memastikan bahwa mereka mempunyai kapabilitas untuk melakukan inovasi bisnis. Selain itu, instrumen pertanyaan telah didesain sesuai dengan literasi dari beberapa penelitian sebelumnya (Wolff, Pett, & Ring, 2015; Ugaddan, Oh & Park, 2016; Iqbal et al., 2021) untuk menghindari adanya *common method bias*. Survey ini dilakukan pada bulan Februari/Maret 2022.

Model struktural untuk model uji coba dalam penelitian ini, dapat dilihat pada Gambar 1. Model tersebut dilandaskan pada teori RBV, dimana teori tersebut berfokus pada sumber daya sebagai komponen internal organisasi dan meningkatkan kinerja dan daya saing perusahaan. Penelitian sebelumnya telah menemukan adanya keterkaitan antara orientasi kewirausahaan, komitmen organisasi dan kinerja inovasi (Ugaddan, Oh & Park, 2016; Kee & Rahman, 2020). Ketika sumber daya internal seperti orientasi kewirausahaan dikaitkan dengan RBV, hal tersebut mampu mendorong perusahaan untuk meningkatkan komitmen organisasi. RBV juga dapat meningkatkan aset tidak berwujud seperti sumber daya manusia, sumber daya manusia tersebut mampu menarik, melatih dan mengembangkan kemampuan inovasi perusahaan dengan meningkatkan komitmen organisasi mereka. Untuk itu, penelitian ini akan menguji bagaimana peran komitmen organisasi dalam memediasi hubungan antara orientasi kewirausahaan dan kinerja inovasi UMKM di wilayah DKI Jakarta, dengan hipotesis sebagai berikut:

H₁ : Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Innovation Performance (IP)

H₂ : Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Organizational Commitment (OC)

H₃ : Organizational Commitment (OC) berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Innovation Performance (IP)

H₄ : Organizational Commitment (OC) memediasi hubungan antara Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) terhadap Innovation Performance (IP)

Model dalam penelitian ini diuji menggunakan aplikasi SmartPLS 3 dengan mengaplikasikan *path weighting scheme*. Sementara prosedur Bootstrapping dilakukan dengan jumlah 170 cases serta 5000 subsamples (Hair et al., 2017) tanpa merubah pengaturan default dari SmartPLS.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Untuk lebih memahami tahapan dalam menguji model tersebut, artikel ini akan menjelaskan prosedur tahap demi tahap sebagai berikut:

Langkah Pertama : Merancang Model Pengukuran (*Outer Model*)

Dalam SEM, variabel laten harus diukur dengan variabel teramati (indikator, item atau variabel manifes). Model pengukuran (*outer model*) digunakan untuk menentukan hubungan antara variabel laten dan indikatornya. Lebih tepatnya, setiap konstruk memiliki model pengukuran (*outer model*) yang menentukan hubungan antara setiap konstruk (lingkaran) dan variabel indikatornya (persegi panjang). Dalam menentukan model pengukuran untuk setiap konstruksya, terdapat dua pilihan model pengukuran yaitu reflektif dan formatif. Secara umum, terdapat dua cara yang berbeda dalam mengukur variabel laten (Sarstedt et al., 2014). Cara pertama adalah menghubungkan konstruk laten ke arah indikator atau yang biasa disebut sebagai pengukuran reflektif. Dalam Gambar 1, laten variabel OC dan IP yang dilambangkan dengan ξ_2 dan η_1 menggunakan model pengukuran reflektif. Cara kedua adalah menghubungkan indikator ke arah konstruk laten atau yang biasa disebut sebagai pengukuran formatif. Dalam Gambar 1, laten variabel EO yang dilambangkan dengan ξ_1 menggunakan model pengukuran formatif.

Dalam model pengukuran reflektif, variabel laten merupakan penyebab dari indikator pengukuran reflektif, dimana indikator pengukuran reflektif mencerminkan hasil atau konsekuensi yang dapat diamati dari efektivitas variabel laten. Sebaliknya, dalam model pengukuran formatif variabel laten dipahami sebagai konsekuensi dari indikator pengukuran formatif dimana variabel laten mewakili kombinasi linier yang tepat atau bebas dari kesalahan pengukuran (Fornell & Bookstein, 1982; Edwards & Bagozzi, 2000; Diamantopoulos, 2011). Model persamaan indikator reflektif dapat ditulis persamaannya sebagai berikut:

$$x = \lambda_x \xi + \delta$$

$$y = \lambda_y \eta + \varepsilon$$

Di mana x dan y adalah indikator untuk variabel laten eksogen (ξ) dan endogen (η). Sedangkan λ_x dan λ_y merupakan matriks *outer loadings* yang menggambarkan seperti koefisien regresi sederhana yang menghubungkan variabel laten dengan indikatornya. Residual yang diukur dengan δ dan ε dapat diinterpretasikan sebagai kesalahan pengukuran atau *noise*. Sementara model persamaan indikator formatif ditulis persamaannya sebagai berikut:

$$x = \pi_x \xi$$

$$y = \pi_y \eta$$

Di mana x dan y adalah indikator untuk variabel laten eksogen (ξ) dan endogen (η). Sedangkan π_x dan π_y merupakan matriks *outer weights* yang menggambarkan yang menghubungkan variabel indikator dengan variabel latennya.

Langkah Kedua : Merancang Model Struktural (*Inner Model*)

Setelah model pengukuran terbentuk, langkah berikutnya adalah merancang model struktural (*inner model*). Menurut Hair et al. (2017) evaluasi model struktural (*inner model*) bertujuan

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

untuk memprediksi hubungan antar variabel laten. Dimana variabel laten endogen diidentifikasi dalam model struktural dengan notasi η dan variabel laten eksogen dengan notasi ξ . Gambar 1 menunjukkan bagaimana variabel eksogen dan endogen terhubung satu sama lain dan dapat diidentifikasi dengan notasi-notasi yang ada.

Gambar 1.
Ilustrasi Model Struktural
Bernotasi

Di mana notasi-notasi yang digunakan adalah:

- ξ_1 = Ksi, variabel laten eksogen EO
- η_1 = Eta, variabel laten endogen OC
- η_2 = Eta, variabel laten endogen IP
- x = Variabel teramati eksogen
- y = Variabel teramati endogen
- λ_x = Lambda, loading faktor variabel latent eksogen
- λ_y = Lambda, loading faktor variabel latent endogen
- β = Beta, koefisien pengaruh variabel endogen terhadap variabel endogen
- γ = Gamma, koefisien pengaruh variabel eksogen terhadap variabel endogen
- ζ = Zeta, galat model
- δ = Delta, galat pengukuran pada variabel manifest untuk variabel laten eksogen
- ε = Epsilon (kecil), galat pengukuran pada variabel manifest untuk variabel laten endogen

Model persamaan struktural diatas dapat ditulis persamaannya sebagai berikut:

$$\eta_1 = \gamma_1 \xi_1 + \zeta_1$$

$$\eta_2 = \beta_1 \eta_1 + \gamma_2 \xi_1 + \zeta_2$$

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

5. Prosedur/Tahapan Evaluasi Model PLS-SEM

Dalam mengevaluasi model PLS-SEM, terdapat dua tahap pengujian yang telah diilustrasikan pada Gambar 2. Tahapan 1 menguji model pengukuran (*outer model evaluation*), pengujian tersebut dilakukan dengan melihat apakah model mencakup model pengukuran reflektif (Tahapan 1.1), model pengukuran formatif (Tahapan 1.2) atau bahkan keduanya. Jika evaluasi model pengukuran memberikan hasil yang memuaskan dan dinyatakan lolos uji, peneliti dapat melanjutkan ke Tahapan 2, yang melibatkan evaluasi model struktural. Secara garis besar, Tahapan 1 mengkaji teori pengukuran, sedangkan Tahapan 2 mencakup teori struktural yang digunakan untuk menentukan apakah hubungan struktural signifikan maupun menguji hipotesis.

Gambar 2.
Tahapan Evaluasi PLS-SEM

Tahapan 1.1 : Mengevaluasi Model Pengukuran Reflektif

Ketika penelitian memiliki model pengukuran reflektif, peneliti dapat memulai memeriksa nilai indikator *loadings*. Ketika nilai *loadings* berada di atas 0.50, mengindikasikan bahwa konstruk tersebut dapat dijelaskan oleh varians indikator terkait sebesar 50%. Nilai *loadings* didapatkan melalui prosedur PLS Algorithm pada aplikasi SmartPLS. Gambar 3 dan Tabel 4 menunjukkan hasil dimana nilai *loadings* pada masing-masing indikator telah mampu menjelaskan konstruk latennya diatas 50%, namun batas minimum *loadings* akan berbeda-beda dan bergantung pada metodologi dan tujuan penelitian yang digunakan (lihat kajian permasalahan ketiga).

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Gambar 3.
Hasil Pengujian Dengan Prosedur PLS-Algorithm

Kriteria evaluasi model pengukuran reflektif selanjutnya adalah *average variance extracted* (AVE). Nilai tersebut masuk dalam pengujian *convergent validity*, pengujian tersebut mengukur sejauh mana konstruk konvergen dalam indikatornya dengan menjelaskan varians item. *Convergent validity* dinilai dengan *average variance extracted* (AVE) untuk semua item yang terkait dengan setiap konstruk. Nilai AVE dihitung sebagai rata-rata beban kuadrat untuk semua indikator yang terkait dengan suatu konstruk. AVE yang dapat diterima adalah 0.50 atau lebih tinggi, karena menunjukkan bahwa rata-rata, konstruk menjelaskan lebih dari 50% varians item-itemnya (lihat Tabel 4).

Tabel 4.
Hasil Pengujian Model Pengukuran Reflektif

Measures		Loadings	Weights	Sources
Entrepreneurial Orientation (Formative Construct)				Wolff, Pett, and Ring (2015)
EO_1	Being first to the market with innovative new products/services		0.102	
EO_2	Bold acts to achieve the goals		0.159	
EO_3	Exploiting risky market opportunities		0.306	
EO_4	Experimenting with new products and service		0.206	
EO_5	Initiating actions to which competitors respond		0.258	
EO_6	Proactively pursuing market opportunities		0.178	

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Measures		Loadings	Weights	Sources
Organizational Commitment (Refelctive Construct)				Ugaddan, Oh and Park (2016)
OC_1	I feel emotionally attached to this firm	0.898		
OC_2	I feel a strong sense of belonging to my firm	0.942		
OC_3	One of the major reasons why I do not leave this firm is that I feel a sense of moral obligation to remain	0.914		
OC_4	If I got another offer for a better job elsewhere I would not feel it was right to leave my firm	0.898		
OC_5	Too much in my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my firm now	0.894		
OC_6	It would be very hard for me to leave my agency right now, even if I wanted to	0.878		
OC_7	I am afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without having another one lined up	0.874		
Innovation Performance (Refelctive Construct)				Iqbal et al. (2021)
IP_1	My firm shows the willingness to support creativity	0.836		
IP_2	My firms takes the risk to venture into new unknown markets	0.902		
IP_3	My firm looks for market opportunities	0.848		

Setelah memenuhi kriteria pengujian pada *convergent validity*, maka kriteria selanjutnya yang perlu diuji adalah permasalahan terkait dengan *discriminant validity* pada setiap konstruk dengan nilai korelasi antar konstuk dalam model (Wong, 2016). Untuk mengukur validitas diskriminan, Wong (2016) menyebutkan terdapat beberapa langkah pengujian yaitu *fornell larcker criterion*, *heterotrait monotrait ratio of correlations* (HTMT) serta *cross loadings*. Tabel 5 memberikan ilustrasi bagaimana pengujian *fornell larcker criterion* telah memenuhi syarat pengujian, dimana korelasi akar kuadrat AVE dengan konstruk yang dituju lebih tinggi dibandingkan akar kuadrat AVE dengan konstruk lain. Sebagai catatan tambahan, ketika peneliti menilai kriteria *fornell larcker criterion* pada model yang mencakup konstruk dengan model pengukuran formatif, peneliti hanya perlu membandingkan nilai akar kuadrat AVE pada konstruk reflektif dengan semua korelasi variabel laten. Namun, menurut Hair et al. (2017), akar kuadrat AVE dari konstruksi yang diukur secara formatif tidak boleh dibandingkan dengan korelasi. Faktanya, seperti yang ditunjukkan pada Tabel 5, akar kuadrat AVE bahkan tidak dilaporkan untuk konstruksi formatif di SmartPLS.

Tabel 5.

Hasil Pengujian Fornell Larcker Criterion

	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
Entrepreneurial Orientation			
Innovation Performance	0.804	0.863	Formatif
Organizational Commitment	0.881	0.763	0.900

Jika merujuk pada pendapat Henseler et al. (2015) yang telah dijelaskan pada bab sebelumnya, menyatakan bahwa pendekatan *fornell larcker criterion* gagal untuk mengidentifikasi

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

discriminant validity pada sebagian kasus besar. Peneliti disarankan untuk menilai *discriminant validity* menggunakan *heterotrait monotrait ratio of correlations* (HTMT). Ramayah et al. (2016) menjelaskan bahwa jika peneliti menemukan nilai HTMT lebih kecil daripada HTMT_{0.85} (Kline, 2015) atau nilai HTMT_{0.90} (Gold et al., 2001) seperti yang ditunjukkan oleh Tabel 6, nilai HTMT telah ditemukan lebih kecil daripada HTMT_{0.85}. Hal tersebut dapat disimpulkan bahwa tidak terdapat masalah pada *discriminant validity*.

Tabel 6.

Hasil Pengujian HTMT Criterion

	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
Innovation Performance		
Organizational Commitment	0.854	

Selanjutnya, alternatif lain dalam menguji permasalahan pada *discriminant validity* adalah menguji HTMT_{inference} melalui prosedur *bootstrapping* dengan melihat nilai *confidence interval*. Tabel 7 menunjukkan nilai *confidence interval* (CI), dimana jika nilai tersebut ditemukan kurang dari sama dengan 1.00 pada CI (2.5%) maupun pada CI (97.5%), hal tersebut dapat diidentifikasi bahwa tidak terdapat masalah pada validitas diskriminan (Henseler et al., 2015).

Tabel 7.

Hasil Pengujian HTMT Inference

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
Entrepreneurial Orientation -> Innovation Performance	0.588	0.611	0.392	0.854
Entrepreneurial Orientation -> Organizational Commitment	0.881	0.882	0.839	0.924
Organizational Commitment -> Innovation Performance	0.245	0.224	-0.060	0.453
Entrepreneurial Orientation -> Organizational Commitment -> Innovation Performance	0.216	0.198	-0.055	0.404

Tahap selanjutnya dalam menguji *discriminant validity* adalah dengan melihat nilai pengujian *cross loadings*. Suatu indikator dinyatakan valid jika mempunyai korelasi *loadings* antar konstruk yang dituju lebih tinggi dibandingkan korelasi *loadings* dengan konstruk lain (lihat Tabel 8). Dengan demikian, konstruk laten memprediksi indikator pada blok mereka lebih baik dibandingkan dengan indikator di blok yang lain (Hair et al., 2017).

Tabel 8.

Hasil Pengujian Cross Loadings

	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
EO_1	0.646	0.558	0.534
EO_2	0.683	0.625	0.533
EO_3	0.870	0.705	0.761
EO_4	0.892	0.714	0.789

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
EO_5	0.868	0.676	0.785
EO_6	0.847	0.618	0.804
IP_1	0.640	0.836	0.618
IP_2	0.727	0.902	0.696
IP_3	0.710	0.848	0.658
OC_1	0.802	0.696	0.898
OC_2	0.826	0.738	0.942
OC_3	0.802	0.704	0.914
OC_4	0.770	0.627	0.898
OC_5	0.785	0.679	0.894
OC_6	0.765	0.654	0.878
OC_7	0.795	0.702	0.874

Ketika peneliti telah memastikan validitas konstruk, uji reliabilitas dilakukan dengan menggunakan uji *composite reliability* dan *cronbach's alpha* dengan melihat seluruh nilai variabel laten memiliki nilai *composite reliability* > 0.7 maupun *cronbach's alpha* dan ρ_a 0.6, dimana hal tersebut dapat disimpulkan bahwa konstruk memiliki reabilitas yang baik atau kuesioner yang digunakan sebagai alat dalam penelitian telah andal atau konsisten. Tabel 4 menunjukkan semua nilai konsistensi reliabilitas internal telah memenuhi syarat. Sebagai catatan tambahan, *cronbach's alpha* merupakan batas bawah dan *composite reliability* merupakan batas atas dari konsistensi internal reliabilitas (Hair et al., 2017).

Tahapan 1.2 : Mengevaluasi Model Pengukuran Formatif

Untuk mengevaluasi model pengukuran formatif, terdapat perbedaan yang cukup signifikan dengan cara mengevaluasi model pada pengukuran reflektif. *Convergent validity* pada model pengukuran formatif ditentukan berdasarkan sejauh mana konstruk yang diukur secara formatif berkorelasi dengan konstruk yang diukur secara reflektif yang memiliki arti yang sama dengan konstruk yang diukur secara formatif (Sarstedt et al., 2014). Penelitian yang dilakukan oleh Hair et al. (2017) menyarankan bahwa konstruk yang diukur secara formatif harus menjelaskan setidaknya 65% varians item yang diukur secara reflektif, yang ditunjukkan oleh koefisien jalur sekitar 0.80. Namun, dalam kebanyakan kasus, koefisien jalur 0.70 juga dapat diterima. Untuk mengevaluasi secara lebih spesifik, peneliti disarankan untuk melihat signifikansi dari nilai *weights* melalui prosedur *bootstrapping* dengan subsampel yang disarankan sebesar 5000. Dengan menggunakan subsampel 5000, peneliti dapat menghitung kesalahan standar *bootstrapping*, yang memungkinkan penghitungan t-value (dan p-value) untuk setiap bobot indikator dari pengukuran reflektif. Berdasarkan t-value, signifikansi *weight* dapat ditentukan untuk membuat keputusan berikut (1) Jika nilai *weight* ditemukan signifikan secara statistik, indikator tersebut dapat dipertahankan, (2) Jika nilai *weight* ditemukan tidak signifikan tetapi nilai *loadings* adalah 0.50 atau lebih tinggi, indikator tersebut masih diperbolehkan untuk dipertahankan, namun hal ini harus didukung dengan teori dan penilaian ahli, (3) Jika nilai *weight* tidak signifikan dan bebannya rendah (yaitu, di bawah 0.50), indikator harus dihapus dari model pengukuran.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Namun demikian, menghilangkan indikator formatif dari model, disarankan untuk dihindari. Hal tersebut dikarenakan setiap indikator dari model formatif merepresentasikan dimensi makna dari variabel laten. Untuk itu, menghilangkan indikator dalam model formatif sama dengan menghilangkan dimensi makna, menyebabkan makna variabel laten berubah (Garson, 2016). Hal tersebut tidak seperti model pengukuran reflektif, indikator formatif tidak dapat dipertukarkan. Oleh karena itu, menghapus indikator formatif memiliki konsekuensi yang merugikan bagi validitas isi model pengukuran (Hair et al., 2014).

Tabel 9.

*Hasil Pengujian Model
Pengukuran Formatif*

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Outer VIF
EO_1 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.102	0.100	0.058	1.760	0.049	1.670
EO_2 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.159	0.162	0.059	2.675	0.008	1.713
EO_3 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.306	0.305	0.063	4.881	0.000	2.474
EO_4 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.206	0.204	0.078	2.637	0.009	3.444
EO_5 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.258	0.259	0.080	3.242	0.001	2.915
EO_6 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.178	0.176	0.074	2.409	0.016	2.737

Selain melihat kriteria-kriteria diatas, evaluasi model pengukuran formatif dilakukan dengan melihat nilai *outer* VIF. Untuk menilai tingkat kolinearitas antara indikator formatif, peneliti harus menghitung *variance inflation factor* (VIF). Dalam menentukan batas nilai, VIF yang lebih tinggi menyiratkan bahwa adanya tingkat kolinearitas yang lebih besar antar indikator. Sebagai batas, nilai VIF di atas lima mengindikasikan kolinearitas antar indikator (lihat Tabel 9).

Tahapan 2 : Mengevaluasi Model Struktural

Selama penilaian model pengukuran menunjukkan bahwa kualitas model pengukuran memuaskan, peneliti dapat melanjutkan ke Tahapan kedua dari proses evaluasi PLS-SEM (Gambar 2), yaitu mengevaluasi model struktural. Berbeda dengan CB-SEM yang memiliki beberapa kriteria *goodness-of-fit* (GOF), PLS-SEM memiliki standar yang lain yaitu penilaian kualitas model didasarkan pada kemampuannya untuk memprediksi konstruksi endogen. Peneliti bisa merujuk kepada kriteria koefisien determinasi (R^2), *cross-validated redundancy* (Q^2) dan model fit. Namun sebelum melakukan beberapa kriteria pengujian tersebut, peneliti harus menguji potensi kolinearitas pada model struktural antara konstruk eksogen (*inner* VIF). Dalam menilai model dengan PLS-SEM, dimulai dengan melihat *R-Square* (R^2) untuk setiap variabel laten endogen. *R-Square* (R^2) atau nilai koefisien determinasi menunjukkan seberapa besar variabel eksogen menjelaskan variabel endogennya. Nilai *R-Square* (R^2) adalah nol sampai dengan satu, apabila nilai *R-Square* (R^2) semakin mendekati satu, maka variabel-

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

variabel eksogen memberikan semua informasi yang dibutuhkan untuk memprediksi variasi variabel endogen. Nilai *R-Square* (R^2) memiliki kelemahan yaitu nilai *R-Square* (R^2) akan meningkat setiap ada penambahan satu variabel eksogen meskipun variabel eksogen tersebut tidak berpengaruh signifikan terhadap variabel endogen.

Tabel 10.

Hasil Pengujian Relevansi Prediktif

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2 (=1 - SSE/SSO)$	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Entrepreneurial Orientation	1020.000	1020.000			
Innovation Performance	510.000	265.564	0.479	0.660	0.656
Organizational Commitment	1190.000	450.835	0.621	0.776	0.775

Menurut Hair et al. (2011, 2017), sebagai pedoman, nilai *R-Squared* sebesar 0.25, 0.50, dan 0.75 mewakili level lemah, sedang, dan substansial. Namun, jika *R-Squared adjusted* yang digunakan (Hair et al., 2017), koefisien ini dapat menjadi bias ke atas dalam model kompleks di mana lebih banyak jalur mengarah ke konstruksi endogen. Berdasarkan ilustrasi yang ditunjukkan oleh Tabel 9, ditemukan variabel IO dapat dijelaskan sebesar 65.6% oleh variabel eksogennya, hal tersebut dikarenakan adanya temuan nilai *R-Square* (R^2) sebesar 0.656. Sementara itu, variabel OC dapat dijelaskan sebesar 77.5% oleh variabel eksogennya, hal tersebut dikarenakan adanya temuan nilai *R-Square* (R^2) sebesar 0.775.

Kriteria selanjutnya adalah mengevaluasi *cross-validated redundancy* (Q^2) untuk mengukur seberapa baik nilai observasi dihasilkan dari model struktural. Menurut Hair et al. (2017), jika nilai Q^2 lebih besar dari nol untuk variabel laten endogen tertentu menunjukkan model jalur PLS-SEM memiliki nilai *predictive relevance*. Nilai statistik tersebut diperoleh dengan teknik penggunaan ulang sampel yang disebut "*Blindfolding*" di mana jarak penghilangan diatur antara 5 dan 12, di mana jumlah pengamatan dibagi dengan jarak penghilangan bukan merupakan bilangan bulat (Hair et al., 2012). Misalnya, jika memilih jarak penghilangan 7, maka setiap titik data ketujuh dihilangkan dan parameter diperkirakan dengan titik data yang tersisa. Menurut Hair et al. (2017), poin data yang dihilangkan dianggap nilai yang hilang dan diganti dengan nilai rata-rata. Parameter yang diperkirakan membantu memprediksi titik data yang dihilangkan dan perbedaan antara titik data yang sebenarnya dihilangkan dan titik data yang diprediksi menjadi masukan untuk perhitungan Q^2 . *Blindfolding* hanya diterapkan pada konstruksi endogen dengan indikator reflektif. Jika Q^2 lebih besar dari nol, hal tersebut menunjukkan nilai *predictive relevance* pada model jalur dalam konteks konstruksi endogen dan indikator reflektif yang sesuai.

Peneliti harus bersikap hati-hati dalam melaporkan dan menggunakan kriteria model fit pada PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2017). Hal tersebut bukan tanpa alasan, kriteria tersebut masih dalam tahap awal penelitian dan belum sepenuhnya disetujui oleh ahli metodologi statistik (misalnya, nilai ambang batas). Meskipun demikian, beberapa peneliti mulai melaporkan model fit dalam metode PLS-SEM. SmartPLS telah menyediakannya beberapa kriteria model fit, namun nilai-nilai tersebut masih perlu dikaji berulang kali untuk dapat diterapkan secara tepat. Di beberapa penelitian terdahulu, kriteria tersebut tidak dilaporkan atau digunakan untuk penilaian hasil

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2017). Untuk itu Hair et al. (2017) menyarankan peneliti untuk menggunakan nilai SRMR, RMS_{θ} , atau *Exact Fit*. Namun dikarenakan belum adanya riset mendalam mengenai tiga kriteria tersebut, peneliti disarankan untuk mengikuti pendekatan konservatif, yaitu jika nilai SRMR kurang dari 0.08 dan Nilai RMS_{θ} kurang dari 0.12, maka model fit dapat diterima. Sebagai catatan, Hair et al. (2017) melarang untuk menggunakan kriteria GOF (yang diajukan oleh Tenenhaus et al., 2004) untuk mengevaluasi pengujian ini (lihat bagian sebelumnya pada kajian temuan masalah).

Menguji Hipotesis Penelitian

Tahap ini bertujuan untuk menguji bagaimana variabel laten eksogen terhubung dengan variabel laten endogen. Untuk menguji hipotesis yang telah diajukan, peneliti dapat melihat nilai koefisien jalur, nilai *T-Statistic* dan *p-value* melalui prosedur *bootstrapping*. Dalam menjalankan prosedur *bootstrapping*, Hair et al. (2017) menegaskan bahwa peneliti harus menggunakan metode *Bias-Corrected and Accelerated (BCa) Bootstrap* menilai signifikansi koefisien jalur dalam model struktural. Sebagai alternatif, peneliti dapat kembali ke nilai *p-value* (<0.05).

Gambar 4.
*Hasil Pengujian Prosedur
 Bootstrapping*

Hair et al. (2014) menjelaskan bahwa nilai koefisien jalur selalu berada pada rentang nilai -1 hingga +1, dimana nilai koefisien jalur yang mendekati +1 merepresentasikan hubungan positif yang kuat dan nilai koefisien jalur yang -1 mengindikasikan hubungan negatif yang kuat. Berdasarkan hasil pengujian koefisien jalur pada Gambar 4 dan Tabel 11, dapat diketahui bahwa semua hubungan memiliki arah hubungan positif dikarenakan nilainya mendekati +1.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Selanjutnya peneliti dapat melihat nilai *T-Statistic* untuk melihat nilai signifikansi antar konstruk. Batas untuk menolak dan menerima hipotesis yang diajukan adalah ± 1.96 , yang mana apabila nilai t-statistik berada pada dibawah 1.96 maka hipotesis akan ditolak atau dengan kata lain menerima hipotesis nol (H_0).

Tabel 11.

Hasil Pengujian Hipotesis Penelitian

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Direct					
EO -> IP	0.588	0.611	0.114	5.160	0.000
EO -> OC	0.881	0.882	0.022	39.628	0.000
OC -> IP	0.245	0.224	0.121	2.026	0.043
Indirect					
EO -> OC -> IP	0.216	0.198	0.107	2.017	0.044

Berdasarkan hasil pengujian, dapat diketahui bahwa seluruh hipotesis dalam penelitian ini diterima, hal tersebut dikarenakan adanya temuan nilai p-values dibawah 0.05. EO ditemukan mampu secara langsung meningkatkan IP dengan arah positif ($\beta=0.588$) dan signifikan ($t=5.160$), untuk itu, semakin tinggi orientasi kewirausahaan yang dimiliki oleh individu, maka semakin tinggi pula kinerja inovasi mereka. Temuan selanjutnya adalah adanya pengaruh antara EO terhadap OC dengan arah positif ($\beta=0.881$) dan signifikan ($t=39.628$), maka dapat disimpulkan bahwa semakin tinggi orientasi kewirausahaan yang dimiliki oleh individu, akan mendorong komitmen organisasi mereka. Pada pengujian hipotesis langsung selanjutnya, ditemukan adanya pengaruh OC terhadap IP dengan arah positif ($\beta=0.245$) dan signifikan ($t=2.026$), maka dapat disimpulkan bahwa semakin tinggi komitmen organisasi yang dimiliki oleh individu, akan mendorong kinerja inovasi mereka.

Menganalisis Peran Mediasi

Efek mediasi digunakan untuk melihat hubungan antara variabel eksogen dan endogen melalui variabel penghubung. Pengaruh variabel eksogen terhadap variabel endogen tidak secara langsung terjadi, namun melalui proses transformasi yang diwakili oleh variabel mediasi (Baron & Kenny, 1986). Pengujian efek mediasi sebenarnya dapat dilakukan dengan menggunakan teknik regresi, namun pada model yang kompleks atau banyaknya jalur yang mengarah kepada konstruk endogen, maka teknik regresi menjadi tidak lagi efisien. Metode *Variance Accounted For* (VAF) yang dikembangkan oleh (Preacher & Hayes, 2008) serta *bootstrapping* dalam distribusi pengaruh tidak langsung dipandang lebih sesuai karena tidak memerlukan asumsi apapun tentang distribusi variabel sehingga dapat diaplikasikan pada ukuran sampel kecil.

Namun, metode VAF hanya dapat dilakukan dengan pertimbangan beberapa kondisi seperti (1) pengaruh langsung variabel eksogen terhadap variabel endogen harus signifikan, (2) setiap jalur yaitu variabel eksogen terhadap variabel mediasi serta variabel mediasi terhadap variabel

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

endogen harus signifikan untuk memenuhi kondisi ini. Jika kedua kondisi diatas telah didapatkan, peneliti dapat menggunakan formula VAF, yaitu pengaruh variabel independen pada variabel mediasi dikalikan dengan pengaruh variabel mediasi pada variabel dependen (Hair et al., 2014). Apabila pengaruh tidak langsung signifikan, maka hal ini menunjukkan bahwa variabel pemediasi mampu menyerap atau mengurangi pengaruh langsung pada pengujian pertama. Berikut adalah formula VAF:

$$VAF = \frac{\text{indirect effect}}{\text{total effect}} \dots\dots \text{Sarstedt et al. (2014)}$$

Ketika peneliti menemukan nilai VAF diatas 80%, maka nilai tersebut menunjukkan peran mediasi penuh (*full mediation*). Dikategorikan sebagai pemediasi parsial apabila nilai VAF berkisar antara 20% sampai dengan 80%, namun jika nilai VAF kurang dari 20% dapat disimpulkan bahwa hampir tidak ada efek mediasi.

Keterangan
 p1 → Jalur antara Eksogen dengan Mediator
 p2 → Jalur antara Mediator dengan Endogen

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Gambar 5.*Pohon Keputusan Peran Mediasi*

Namun dalam kajian selanjutnya, Hair et al. (2017) merevisi cara di atas dengan menyarankan untuk tidak lagi melihat nilai VAF, namun menyarankan agar melihat perubahan efek yang ada (lihat Gambar 5) dari hubungan langsung ke tidak langsung dengan kondisi sebagai berikut (1) *Direct-only nonmediation*, kondisi ditemukan apabila efek langsung signifikan, namun tidak dengan efek tidak langsung; (2) *No-effect nonmediation*, kondisi dimana efek langsung maupun tidak langsung ditemukan tidak signifikan; (3) *Complementary mediation*, kondisi ini ditemukan ketika efek tidak langsung dan efek langsung ditemukan signifikan dan mengarah ke arah yang sama; (4) *Competitive mediation*, kondisi dimana efek tidak langsung dan efek langsung ditemukan signifikan namun memiliki arah yang berlawanan; (5) *Indirect-only mediation*, merupakan kondisi dimana efek tidak langsung signifikan namun tidak dengan efek langsung. Tabel 11 mengilustrasikan bagaimana variabel mediasi yaitu OC ditemukan memiliki peran mediasi *complementary mediation*, hal tersebut dikarenakan ditemukannya efek hubungan langsung (EO→IP) dan tidak langsung (EO→OC→IP) berpengaruh signifikan ($t=2.017$) dan mengarah ke arah yang sama ($\beta=0.216$).

6. Catatan Penutup

Keputusan atas penggunaan metode CB-SEM atau PLS-SEM tidak didasarkan pada metode mana yang lebih baik. Jika peneliti ingin kembali lagi kepada dasar pengembangan metodologi statistik, mereka akan memahami “bagaimana” dan “untuk apa” masing-masing metode tersebut dikembangkan. Selain itu, keputusan penggunaannya juga tidak didasarkan pada satu asumsi dan seakan-akan tidak melihat asumsi yang lain, sebagai contoh, peneliti terapan sering memutuskan untuk menggunakan PLS-SEM karena keterbatasan sampel yang kecil, namun jarang dari peneliti yang mempertimbangkan batas minimum nilai (seperti batas nilai *loadings*) yang diperlukan untuk menutupi kekurangan sampel yang ada. Ketika seorang peneliti memutuskan untuk menggunakan SEM-PLS dengan contoh alasan tersebut, peneliti juga akan dihadapkan pada pemenuhan kriteria asumsi lain yang mampu menutupi kekurangan yang ada. Alasan pemilihan yang umum lainnya adalah PLS-SEM dipersepsikan sebagai metode pilihan utama ketika peneliti dihadapkan pada data yang tidak berdistribusi secara normal, namun peneliti tetap memaksakan keinginan mereka untuk menguji model empiris dengan menggunakan kriteria *goodness-of-fit* yang berlebihan, sementara disisi lain, para ahli metodologi statistik masih berusaha untuk menetapkan kriteria model fit untuk PLS-SEM.

Peneliti yang sesungguhnya akan mengambil keputusan secara bijak dengan mempertimbangkan segala situasi dan kondisi yang mereka hadapi. Singkatnya, baik CB-SEM dan PLS-SEM memiliki perbedaan estimasi parameter dan aturan penggunaan. Oleh sebab itu, Peneliti terapan harus mempertimbangkan banyak asumsi ketika akan memutuskan untuk menerapkan PLS-SEM dalam penelitiannya, sebagai contoh, jika penelitian yang dilakukan merupakan penelitian *confirmatory*, peneliti disarankan untuk menggunakan metode CB-SEM. Penulis berharap, artikel ini dapat membantu peneliti terapan untuk memutuskan metode mana yang akan diterapkan untuk penelitian kuantitatif yang sedang mereka jalankan, serta

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

memberikan gambaran yang jelas mengenai prosedur dan tahapan penggunaan metode PLS-SEM.

7. Daftar Pustaka

1. Dijkstra TK. Latent variables and indices: Herman world's basic design and partial least squares. In V. Esposito Vinzi, W. W. Chin, J. Henseler, H. Wang (Eds.), *Handbook of partial least squares: Concepts, methods and applications* (Springer Handbooks of Computational Statistics Series). Heidelberg/Dordrecht/ London/New York: Springer. 2010;II:23-46.
2. Jöreskog KG, Wold HOA. The ML and PLS techniques for modeling with latent variables: Historical and comparative aspects. In H. O. A. Wold & K. G. Jöreskog (Eds.), *Systems under indirect observation, part I* (pp. 263–270). Amsterdam: North-Holland; 1982.
3. Rigdon EE. Rethinking partial least squares path modeling: In praise of simple methods. *Long Range Planning*. 2012; 45(5–6):341–358.
4. Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Smith D, Reams R, Hair JF. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): A useful tool for family business researchers. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*. 2014; 5(1):105–115.
5. Antonakis J, Bendahan S, Jacquart P, Lalive R. On making causal claims: A review and recommendations. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 2010;21(6):1086-1120. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2010.10.010>
6. Vandenberg RJ. Introduction: Statistical and methodological myths and urban legends: Where, pray tell, did they get this idea? *Organizational Research Methods*. 2006;9(2):194-201. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428105285506>
7. Rönkkö M, McIntosh CN, Antonakis J, Edwards JR. Partial least squares path modeling: Time for some serious second thoughts. *Journal of Operations Management*. 2016;47:9-27. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2016.05.002>
8. Aguirre-Urreta MI, Marakas GM. A rejoinder to rigdon et al (2014). *Information Systems Research*. 2014;25(4):785-788. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2014.0545>
9. McIntosh CN, Edwards JR, Antonakis J. Reflections on partial least squares path modeling. *Organizational Research Methods*. 2014;17(2):210-251. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428114529165>
10. Goodhue DL, Lewis W, Thompson R. Comparing PLS to regression and LISREL: A response to Marcoulides, Chin and Saunders. *Mis Quarterly*. 2012;703-716. Available:<https://doi.org/10.2307/41703476>
11. Aguirre-Urreta MI, Rönkkö M. Statistical inference with PLS using bootstrap confidence intervals. *MIS Quarterly*, 2018;42(3):1001-1020. Available:<https://doi.org/10.25300/misq/2018/13587>
12. Afthanorhan A, Awang Z, Aimran N. Five common mistakes for using partial least squares path modeling (PLS-PM) in management research. *Contemporary Management Research*. 2020;16(4):255–278.
13. Lohmöller JB. Predictive vs. structural modeling: PLS vs. ML. In *Latent Variable Path Modeling with Partial Least Squares* (pp. 199-226). Physica, Heidelberg; 1989. Available:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-52512-4_5

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

14. Henseler J, Hubona G, Ray PA. Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: Updated guidelines. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*. 2016;116(1):2-20.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1108/imds-09-2015-0382>
15. Hair Jr. JF, Matthews LM, Matthews RL, Sarstedt M. PLS-SEM or CB-SEM: Updated guidelines on which method to use. *International Journal of Multivariate Data Analysis*. 2017;1(2):107-123.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmda.2017.087624>
16. Ringle CM, Sarstedt M, Mitchell R, Gudergan SP. Partial least squares structural equation modeling in HRM research. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 2018;1-27.
17. Sarstedt M, Hair JF, Ringle CM, Thiele KO, Gudergan SP. Estimation issues with PLS and CBSEM: Where the bias lies!. *Journal of Business Research*. 2016;69(10):3998-4010.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.06.00>
18. Schuberth F, Henseler J, Dijkstra TK. Partial least squares path modeling using ordinal categorical indicators. *Quality & Quantity*. 2018;52(1):9-35.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-016-0401-7>
19. Hwang H, Takane Y, Tenenhaus A. An alternative estimation procedure for partial least squares path modeling. *Behavior-metrika*. 2015;42(1):63-78.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.2333/bhmk.42.63>
20. Rönkkö M, McIntosh CN, Antonakis J. On the adoption of partial least squares in psychological research: Caveat emptor. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 2015;87:76-84.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.07.019>
21. Ioannidis JP. Why most published research findings are false. *PLoS Medicine*. 2005; 2(8):e124.
22. Wagenmakers EJ, Wetzels R, Borsboom D, van der Maas HL, Kievit RA. An agenda for purely confirmatory research. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 2012;7(6):632-638.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612463078>
23. Henseler J. Bridging design and behavioral research with variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of Advertising*. 2017;46(1):178-192.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2017.1281780>
24. Tenenhaus M, Amato S, Esposito VV. A global goodness-of-fit index for PLS structural equation modeling. In *Proceedings of the XLII SIS Scientific Meeting*. Padova, Italy: CLEUP. 2004;739–742.
25. Tenenhaus M, Esposito Vinzi V, Chatelin YM, Lauro C. PLS path modeling. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2005;48:159–205.
26. Henseler J, Sarstedt M. Goodness-of-fit indices for partial least squares path modeling. *Computational Statistics*. 2013; 28:565–580.
27. Henseler J, Dijkstra TK, Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Diamantopoulos A, Straub DW, et al. Common beliefs and reality about partial least squares: Comments on Rönkkö & Evermann (2013). *Organizational Research Methods*. 2014;17:182–209.
28. Hu LT, Bentler PM. Fit indices in covariance structure modeling: Sensitivity to under parameterized model misspecification. *Psychological Methods*. 1998;3: 424–453.
29. Dijkstra TK, Henseler J. Consistent partial least squares path modeling. *MIS Quarterly*. 2015b;39:297–316.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

30. Dijkstra TK, Henseler J. Consistent and asymptotically normal PLS estimators for linear structural equations. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2015^a;81:10–23.
31. Henseler J, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 2015;43(1):115-135.
Available:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
32. Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Hair JF. Partial least squares structural equation modeling with R. *Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation*. 2017;21:2017.
33. Polkinghorne DE. Language and meaning: Data collection in qualitative research. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*. 2005; 52(2):137-145. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.52.2.137>
34. James A. Wolff, Timothy L. Pett, J. Kirk Ring. Small firm growth as a function of both learning orientation and entre-preneurial orientation. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*. 2015;21(5):709–730.
35. Ugaddan R, Oh HG, Park SM. An exploration of entrepreneurial orientation and organizational commitment: A focus on the role of public service motivation. *Asian Rev. Public Adm*. 2016;27:4–24.
36. Iqbal S, Moleiro Martins J, Nuno Mata M, Naz S, Akhtar S, Abreu A. Linking entrepreneurial orientation with innovation performance in SMES; the role of organizational commitment and trans-forma-tional leadership using smart PLS-SEM. *Sustainability*. 2021;13(8):4361. MDPI AG.
Available:<http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13084361>
37. Kee D, Rahman NA. Entrepreneurial orientation, innovation and SME performance: A study of SMEs in Malaysia using PLS-SEM. *GATR Global Journal of Business Social Sciences Review*. 2020;8: 73-80.
DOI: 10.35609/gjbssr.2020.8.2(1)
38. Fornell CG, Bookstein FL. Two structural equation models: LISREL and PLS applied to consumer exit-voice theory. *Journal of Marketing Research*. 1982;19(4):440–452.
39. Edwards JR, Bagozzi RP. On the nature and direction of relationships between constructs and measures. *Psychological Methods*. 2000;5(2):155–174.
40. Diamantopoulos A. Incorporating formative measures into covariance-based structural equation models. *MIS Quarterly*. 2011; 35(2):335–358.
41. Wong KK. Mediation analysis, categorical moderation analysis, and higher-order constructs modeling in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM): A B2B Example using SmartPLS, *Marketing Bulletin*, 26, Technical Note 1. 2016;1-22.
42. Ramayah T, Cheah J, Chuah F, Ting H, Memon MA. *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 3.0: An updated and practical guide to statistical analysis*. Singapore: Pearson; 2016.
43. Kline RB. *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. Guilford publications; 2015.
44. Gold AH, Malhotra A, Segars AH. Knowledge management: An organiza-tional capabilities perspective. *Journal of Management Information Systems*. 2001; 18(1):185–214. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2001.11045669>
45. Garson GD. *Partial least squares regression and structural equation models*. Asheboro: Statistical Associates; 2016.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

46. Hair JF, Jr., Hult GTM, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. A primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications Ltd; 2014.
47. Hair JF, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*. 2011;19(2):139–151.
48. Hair JF, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. Partial least squares: The better approach to structural equation modeling? *Long Range Planning*. 2012;45(5–6):312–319.
49. Baron RM, Kenny DA. The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. 1986;51:1173–1182.
50. Preacher KJ, Hayes AF. Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in simple and multiple mediator models. *Behavior Research Methods*. 2008a;40: 879–891.
51. Hair JF, Sarstedt M, Pieper T, Ringle CM. The use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in strategic management research: A review of past practices and recommendations for future applications. *Long Range Planning*. 2012;45:320–340.
52. Hair JF, Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Mena JA. An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 2012;40: 414–433.

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Original Artikel

To cite this article (APA Style):

Putra, W. B. T. S. (2022). Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 14(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2022/v14i130367>

Problems, Common Beliefs and Procedures on the Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research

Wawas Bangun Tegar Sunaryo Putra^{a*}

^a Indonesian School of Research, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analysed, interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/SAJSSE/2022/v14i130367

Open Peer Review History:

This journal follows the Advanced Open Peer Review policy. Identity of the Reviewers, Editor(s) and additional Reviewers, peer review comments, different versions of the manuscript, comments of the editors, etc are available here: <https://www.sdiarticle5.com/review-history/86493>

Original Research Article

Received 18 February 2022

Accepted 28 April 2022

Published 02 May 2022

ABSTRACT

Partial least squares structural equation modeling (commonly referred to as PLS-SEM) was not developed without reason. PLS-SEM was developed as an alternative to covariance-based SEM, allowing researchers to conduct exploratory research. In addition, PLS-SEM is considered capable of providing flexibility related to data characteristics, model complexity, and model specifications. Undoubtedly, PLS-SEM is the most frequently used method in many fields of business research. However, many researchers use PLS-SEM incorrectly and even expect more without understanding the basic structural equation modeling method. For this reason, this article will discuss various types of problems and general beliefs about the use of PLS-SEM in business research. In addition, this article can be used as a reference to make it easier for applied researchers to decide what methods, techniques, and tools will be used to complete their research. In addition, at the end of this article, we will discuss how PLS-SEM can be applied to develop theory in business research through a series of technical introductions taking into account user needs. Subsequently, this article will be equipped with a systematic procedure that discusses the evaluation flow of each PLS-SEM test through illustrations with a notated model using SmartPLS.

Keywords: *Partial least squares; structural equation modeling; Smart-PLS.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In behavioral research, especially in the business field, a large and normally distributed sample size is required to obtain an ideal data set. However, the reality on the ground does not support this. Many applied researchers have only limited respondents, which often happens because of the nature and characteristics of the research itself. Thereby, researchers are often faced with difficulties in carrying out statistical analysis of the data they have, particularly on structural equation modeling (SEM) on latent variables where CB-SEM methods such as LISREL (linear structural relationship) and AMOS (*analysis of moment structures*) has strict data quality assumptions. Hence, the PLS-SEM method is designed as an alternative to CB-SEM for researchers using the SEM approach, which makes it easier to direct model predictions and is considered capable of reducing the requirements to meet data quality and relationship specifications that CB-SEM has set [1,2,3,4].

Herman Wold first proposed the PLS-SEM method in 1982, and the method was introduced as an alternative method to CB-SEM, not as a substitute method. Since the introduction of this method, many studies have emerged that view the incompatibility of the PLS-SEM method in empirical research [5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12]. The study discusses the alleged insurmountable weaknesses in PLS-SEM use and explicitly or implicitly calls for the prohibition and condemnation of the use of PLS-SEM.

On the other hand, studies conducted by Lohmoller [13] and Henseler, Hubona, and Ray [14] stated that PLS-SEM is still relevant if the research has exploratory objectives. Hair et al. [15] specifically mention that a study is exploratory when the research is aimed at finding patterns in data with the assumption of lack/absence of theory or previous literacy on the variables being tested, while confirmatory nature is carried out when the research is aimed at testing hypotheses of theories and concepts. In addition, another reason for the relevance of using the PLS-SEM method is the alleged error in the measurement model specification in previous studies. These errors can be identified if the researcher is unsure of the causal effect or the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous constructs they will test [12]. Thus, PLS-SEM is more appropriate to predict than to estimate the relationship between latent variables or constructs in the hypothesized model.

Although, since the beginning, PLS-SEM has been known as a method for research that has exploratory purposes, several studies have explained that PLS-SEM can be used for both confirmatory and exploratory purposes [16,17,18]. Throughout their discussions, the PLS-SEM method seems to be accepted in many journals or publications for confirmatory purposes because it uses strong theoretical support for established theory testing [12]. Since then, the debate on the true nature of PLS-PM has been endless, specifically on statistical methodologies, and this condition makes applied researchers ignore articles on statistical flaws within PLS-SEM. They use the method in all situations and for various research purposes.

This article will discuss some of the problems that often arise from the inappropriate and excessive use of the PLS-SEM method and return the basic principles of PLS-SEM into structural equation modeling. Researchers need to understand that there are appropriate situations and conditions for PLS-SEM and CB-SEM when conducting data analysis. In other words, there are times when they have to understand why PLS-SEM can/cannot be applied in management research to avoid the decision that PLS-SEM can be used as the main choice in various domains. Applied indeed often finds itself in exhaustion when researchers are asked to decide to use the CB-SEM approach method. The fatigue is due to the necessity to understand CB-SEM use, which requires far more complex and complicated statistical assumptions. As a result, applied researchers always consider that PLS-SEM is a reliable method because it does not require any effort to understand the basics of statistics [12]. The findings from publications that are still the goal of using PLS-SEM for confirmation are questionable because they contradict the original purpose of PLS-SEM, which was developed naturally for exploratory purposes. Therefore, the decision to use PLS-SEM is inappropriate when the research has a confirmatory goal because most previous findings do not meet the current dynamics of progress [12].

In addition to the problems mentioned above, many applied researchers still use inappropriate procedures when carrying out the PLS-SEM method. This article will identify and conduct a study of common mistakes often made by comparing the opinions of various statistical methodologists from various literacy sources. Furthermore, this article will present a systematic

flow for evaluating tests on the PLS-SEM method. The flow will be presented using a notated example with the SmartPLS application. The study in this article is expected to be a reference for applied researchers in adopting the PLS-SEM method and helping them decide which method is appropriate for them to use.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Applied researchers in the social sciences have been familiar with statistical analysis tools for decades. It starts with using univariate and bivariate analysis to understand the data and the relationship between variables. However, along with the transformation that occurred in social research, researchers began to face research models that were quite complex due to the progress of current business dynamics. Therefore, researchers need more sophisticated multivariate data analysis methods to understand the more complex relationships related to the current research direction. *Multivariate analysis* is a statistical method that can simultaneously analyze multiple variables, starting from using the first generation technique, namely cluster analysis, exploratory factor analysis, multidimensional scaling, and developing into the second generation, namely PLS-SEM. On the other hand, in this case, confirmatory research, the first generation technique starts from the analysis of variance, logistic regression, multiple regression, and confirmatory factor analysis, which develops into CB-SEM [15].

Structural equation modeling (SEM) allows researchers to examine complex sets of relationships, where these conditions cannot be done if using another analysis technique. SEM analysis is divided into two types: SEM based on covariance (CB-SEM) and SEM based on partial least squares (PLS-SEM). According to Hair et al. [15], CB-SEM confirms (or rejects) pre-existing theories and hypothetical relationships. This can be done by determining how well the proposed theoretical model can estimate the covariance matrix for the sample data set. Instead, PLS-SEM is used to develop theories in exploratory research that may not have existed before. It can be done by focusing on explaining the variance in the dependent variable when examining the model.

3. CRITICAL REVIEW

1st Problem: Incompatibility of using PLS-SEM

A scientist named Herman Wold first introduced the PLS-SEM method in 1982. This method is the answer to problems that arise from the use of the CB-SEM method, problems that arise include the lack of flexibility related to data characteristics, the development of research models that have high complexity, etc. Initially, PLS-SEM was introduced as an alternative to CB-SEM, which adopted the composite factor method to generate parameter estimates from a latent construct's linear combinations of observed variables, while the method used by CB-SEM is a common factor. Thus, many differences were found between both methods (see Table 1).

Table 1. Composite factor (PLS-SEM) versus common factor (CB-SEM)

Composite Factor Method	Common Factor
Partial Least Squares Path Modeling (PLS-PM)	Maximum Likelihood-based CBSEM (ML-CBSEM)
Generalized Structure Component Analysis (GSCA)	Diagonal Weighted Least Squares (DWLS-CBSEM)
Consistent PLS (PLSc)	Weighted Least Squares Maximum Variance (WLSMV-CBSEM)
Weighted PLS	Asymptotic Distribution Free (ADF-CBSEM)
PLS Predict	Generalized Least Squares (GLS-CBSEM)
Statistical Software	
SmartPLS	AMOS
Warp PLS	LISREL
PLS Graph	MPLUS

Source: Afthanorhan, Awang and Aimran [12]

Composite-based structural equation modeling is known to have three approaches, namely (1) regression on sum scales, (2) generalized structured component analysis, and (3) PLS analysis. The three approaches use ordinary least squares estimation, which aims to obtain path coefficients and loading indicators with the help of an iterative algorithm to minimize the criterion function. However, only "PLS analysis" uses two steps called measurement model estimation and structural modeling [19,20,7]. Some researchers believe that composite-based is the only reason for exploratory purposes because PLS-SEM (composite factor) predicts a more general model than CBSEM and does not consider model specification errors. The estimates obtained are meaningless if the common factor model is not accepted, and thus the common factor is always seen as a confirmatory tool [5,12].

Many researchers revealed that their decision to choose PLS-SEM was based on the belief that PLS-SEM can be used for both confirmatory and exploratory purposes. Hair et al. [15] explain the difference between the two, which explains that a study is exploratory when the research aims to find patterns in a dataset with the assumption of lack/absence of theory or previous literacy on the variables tested, while the confirmatory nature is carried out when the research is aimed at test hypotheses of pre-existing theories and concepts. In short, if the research is aimed at developing a theory, then the research is exploratory. On the other hand, when the research aims to re-examine existing concepts, the research is confirmatory. However, the difference between exploratory and confirmatory research is not as clear-cut as defined; there are many accompanying objective criteria (see Table 2).

Applied researchers need to understand that the two research objectives, both confirmatory and exploratory, have different goals and techniques; not only that, the different criteria that must be met are one of the reasons for researchers to understand the conditions and situations that will lead them to make decisions. When researchers make decisions, not in line with their research objectives and methods, the consequences are irresponsible research results [21], where inappropriate results can lead to conclusions that will impact managerial decisions, it can happen because various perspectives arise when researchers want to carry out their research projects. Situations and conditions like this can

be bad in many ways, such as wrong logic, inappropriate design, and incorrect statistical methods [22]. Henseler [23] argues that the characteristics of latent constructs can determine the character of research designs. Therefore, every factor that describes the behavioral construct should be checked with CBSEM (confirmatory method), while the design-construct should be tested with PLS-SEM (exploratory method).

2nd Problem: Inaccuracy in using the Goodness of Fit (GoF) test

As previously stated, PLS-SEM was developed to be a predictive method. However, methodologists are still trying to develop the PLS-SEM method so that it can be used to test confirmatory research. These efforts can be seen in the development of model fit criteria from time to time. The model fit index allows assessing how well the hypothesized model structure fits the empirical data and helps identify model specification errors [15]. The initial submission of model criteria in PLS-SEM was proposed by Tenenhaus et al. [24] and Tenenhaus et al. [25]. They proposed the GOF criterion, a single measure used to validate the combined performance of the measurement model (outer model) and structural model (inner model). The GoF index value is obtained from the average communalities index and R^2 statistical formula model as follows $GoF = \sqrt{Com \times R^2}$. Tenenhaus et al. [24] proposed the goodness-of-fit (GoF) index as a solution to validate the PLS model globally [24]. However, Henseler and Sarstedt [26] conducted a trial on the index proposed by Tenenhaus et al. [24] on two models, including the conceptual and empirical models. The results of the trials concluded that GOF could not represent the goodness-of-fit criteria in PLS-SEM [26,15]. In addition, GoF, unlike the fit measure in CB-SEM, the criterion cannot separate valid models from invalid ones. Since GoF also does not apply to formatively measured models and cannot meet over-parametric attempts, applied researchers are advised not to use the GoF criteria proposed by Tenenhaus et al. [24].

The stage of developing the model fit criteria was continued by Henseler et al. [27], who assessed the suitability of the standard criteria for the root mean square residual (SRMR), which is a fit index adopted from the CB-SEM method. SRMR was defined as the mean square root difference between the observed and implied-model correlations. The SRMR index is a measure of

absolute fit, where a value of zero indicates a perfect match. In the CB-SEM method, values less than 0.08 are generally considered suitable [28]. However, this threshold is likely too low for PLS-SEM [15]. The statement is not without reason; the differences between the observed correlation and the implied-model correlation play different roles in CB-SEM and PLS-SEM. The CB-SEM algorithm aims to minimize the differences; whether PLS-SEM, the differences result from the model estimates, aiming to maximize the explained variance of the endogenous constructs.

In addition to the SRMR criteria, as a measure of alternative model fit, researchers can use the root mean square residual covariance (RMS_{θ}), which uses the same logic as SRMR but depends on the covariance. These criteria were introduced by Lohmöller [13] but have not been widely explored by PLS-SEM researchers. Initial experimental results show a (conservative) threshold for RMS_{θ} of 0.12. An RMS_{θ} value below 0.12 indicates a suitable model, while a higher value indicates a less suitable model [27]. Finally, Dijkstra and Henseler [29] introduced the exact fit test. The chi-square-based test applies a

bootstrapping procedure to obtain the p-value of the difference between the observed correlation and the correlation implied by the model.

Unlike SRMR, the discrepancy is not expressed in residuals but in terms of distances, which are calculated in two forms (Euclidean and geodesic distance). Initial experimental results showed that SRMR, RMS_{θ} , and Exact Fit Test were able to identify various model specification errors [30,27]. However, those criteria are still too early, or little is known about how these measurement criteria can be accepted for various data and model constellations, so more research is needed to explore other criteria. Moreover, these criteria cannot be easily implemented in standard PLS-SEM software. However, SmartPLS provides SRMR, RMS_{θ} , and exact fit test [15].

Then, is PLS-SEM unable to carry out confirmatory research? Several researchers [16,17,18] agree that PLS-SEM can be used for confirmatory research along with the start of exploring the development of model fit criteria. However, those three eligibility criteria must be met using the PLS-SEM method for confirmatory purposes.

Table 2. Confirmatory versus exploratory

Confirmatory	Exploratory
Replicating an established theory into a new domain	Develop a new model based on lack of evidence or fact
Confirming a pre-specified relationship	Connecting ideas to understand cause-effect
For estimating purpose	For prediction purpose
Statistically significant results	Potential relationships
Definitive answers to hypotheses	Novel relevant questions
For theory-driven	For data-driven
Hypotheses testing methods	
Highest accuracy numerical models	
For theory testing	For theory development (exploration purpose)
Testing a priori hypotheses	Developing promising a posteriori hypothesis
Maximizing the confidence in conclusions	
	Designing efficient experiments
	Reinforcing confirmed conclusion
For the common factor model	For the composite factor model
Modified the existing theory by included a new path or construct	Entirely changing the measurement item in existing theory
Integrating theory	Change the relationships between construct from prior theories (reciprocal relationships)
Example:	Example:
Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty, Trust, Distrust, Attitudinal, Communication, Affective, Emotion, Leadership, Performance	Brand equity, Type of system, Information source, Decision-making perspective, Network structure, Network capability, Technology, Device, Location
Recommendation Method: CB-SEM	Recommendation Method: PLS-SEM

Source: Afthanorhan, Awang & Aimran [12]

3rd Problem: Poor loadings

Many applied researchers switched from CB-SEM to PLS-SEM only because they found the loading values were greater than CB-SEM [12]. On the other hand, there are still differences of opinion on the threshold of the loadings indicator value. According to Hair et al. [15], the significant value of outer loadings is still very weak, so the general rule determined for the outer loadings value threshold is above 0.708. However, applied researchers in the social sciences often find loadings values below 0.70, particularly when they carry out exploratory research. For this reason, researchers are advised to store items with loading values between 0.4 to 0.7 as long as the internal consistency reliability values (In this case, Average Variance Extracted, Composite Reliability, etc.) have met the test requirements. Hence, the decision to take the threshold of loadings must consider many factors and conditions, both from the research objective (exploratory or confirmatory) and the condition of the internal consistency reliability value itself. As a side note, research conducted by Afthanorhan, Awang and Aimran [12] shows a condition where the validity and reliability of a construct are very sensitive and depends on the number of items per construct and the value of the loadings itself; the higher the value of loadings, increasing the AVE and CR values.

4th Problem: Lack of discriminant validity

Discriminant validity is used to see how a construct differs from other constructs by using empirical standards. Thus, testing discriminant validity can help researchers to be able to see whether a construct is different from other constructs, as well as capture phenomena that other constructs in the model may not represent. Traditionally, researchers have relied on two measures of discriminant validity. Cross-loading is usually the first approach to assessing the discriminant validity of an indicator. The next criterion is Fornell-Larcker, where the approach aims to assess discriminant validity by comparing the square root of the AVE value with the correlation of the latent variables. [15]. However, Henseler et al. [31] suggested using HTMT instead of Fornell's larcker criterion. This is based on the failure of the Fornell-Larcker Criterion test to identify discriminant validity in large cases. The Fornell larcker criterion test is carried out by comparing the square root of the AVE for each construct with the correlation value between constructs in the model [15]. A construct

is declared valid if it has the highest AVE square root correlation with the target construct compared to the AVE square root with other constructs. One alternative to the Fornell-Larcker criterion is the heterotrait monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT).

However, the threshold value of HTMT is still debated [15]. Henseler et al. [31] research suggests a threshold value of 0.90 if the path models have very similar conceptual constructs. However, when the constructs in the path model are conceptually much different, a lower threshold value of 0.85 is strongly recommended [31,15]. Subsequently, researchers are advised to look at $HMT_{inference}$ through a bootstrapping procedure with a confidence interval value. As an initial step to running the HMTInference test, a bootstrapping procedure with a subsample of 5000 is executed to obtain the confidence interval value. Subsamples are drawn randomly (with replacement) from the original data set [15]. Then the sub-samples are used to estimate the model, where the process is repeated until the specified number is determined; the recommended sub-samples are 5,000. The parameters estimated from the subsample (in this case, the HTMT statistic) are used to obtain the standard error for the estimate.

Research conducted by Henseler et al. [31] critically tested the cross-loading criteria and the Fornell-Larcker criteria for discriminant validity assessment. The research has found that neither approach can detect discriminant validity issues accurately. They reveal that cross-loading fails to show a lack of discriminant validity when the two constructs are perfectly correlated, making this criterion ineffective for empirical research. Similarly, the Fornell-Larcker criterion performs very poorly, especially when the indicator loadings of the considered constructs differ only slightly. When the variable loading indicator is stronger, the performance of the Fornell-Larcker criterion in detecting discriminant validity problems increases but overall still tends to be poor. In conclusion from the above debate, applied researchers are advised to be able to make decisions by considering the existing situations and conditions, which have been described previously.

1st Common Belief: PLS-SEM selection based on small sample size

PLS-SEM has been recognized as a method that offers special sampling capabilities that other

multivariate analysis tools do not have. However, this is disputed by Sarstedt, Ringle, and Hair [32], who state that, indeed, PLS-SEM can be applied with smaller samples in many cases. However, the legitimacy of the analysis depends on the size and nature of the population (for example, in terms of heterogeneity). No statistical method (including PLS-SEM) can compensate for a poorly designed sample [32].

The decision to use PLS-SEM, which is only based on the availability of a small sample, is not allowed; this is because the estimation method developed by PLS-SEM does not solve the sample problem. If we return to the basic methodology, population sampling is selecting a portion of a group of subjects or respondents who represent the entire population [33]. The size of the estimated sample obtained based on the sampling of the population must be reflected with the actual population to ensure that the actual estimate can answer the research question. To ensure the feasibility of such estimates, sufficient sample sizes are required for statistical methodologies involving a structural equation model approach [12]. Hair et al. [15] suggest using some sample calculations, such as multiplying the sample by five to ten times the number of indicators observed. However, when researchers are faced with a limited/small number of samples, they must look at the criteria for limiting the significance of loadings according to the number of samples they have (see Table 3).

Table 3. Significance loadings based on sample size

Sample Size	Loadings
50	0.75
60	0.70
70	0.65
85	0.60
100	0.55
120	0.50
150	0.45
200	0.40
250	0.35
300	0.30

Source: Hair et al. [15]

2nd Common Belief: PLS-SEM algorithm does simultaneously calculate all the relationships (simultaneously)

As explained in the previous chapter, PLS-SEM is an alternative to CB-SEM, with a different

parameter estimation technique. However, several things need to be clarified concerning the objectives of the current research. Some applied researchers still have expectations that PLS-SEM can carry out simultaneous relationships. Different from CB-SEM, which is based on common factors, the PLS-SEM algorithm does not simultaneously calculate all model relationships (simultaneously) but uses ordinary least squares regressions to estimate the model regression relationships partially – this can be expressed from the name, partial least square [32]. PLS-SEM applies ordinary least squares regressions (OLS) to minimize residual variance from endogenous constructs. Hence, PLS-SEM can estimate the coefficients of the path model relationship that maximizes the R^2 value of the endogenous construct. Therefore PLS-SEM is the recommended method for exploratory research purposes, so PLS-SEM is considered a variance-based approach to SEM.

4. PROCEDURES OF PLS-SEM MODEL SPECIFICATION

To understand how the PLS-SEM method can be applied to exploratory research, the authors conducted a study using a pilot model to understand the effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) in improving SME's Innovation Performance (IP) through Organizational Commitment (OC) as a mediating variable. Overall, this study obtained as many as 170 respondents who are business owners and senior executives from the retail sector MSMEs in the DKI Jakarta area. As one of the efforts in distributing questionnaires, the researcher gave several screening questions related to the respondent's role in the SME's business where they worked. This is done to ensure that they can innovate business. In addition, the question instrument has been designed according to the literacy of several previous studies [34,35,36] to avoid common method bias. This survey was conducted in February/March 2022.

The structural model for in this study can be seen in Fig. 1. The model is based on the RBV theory, where the theory focuses on resources as an internal component of the organization and improves company performance and competitiveness. Previous research has found a link between entrepreneurial orientation, organizational commitment, and innovation performance [35,37]. Internal resources such as entrepreneurial orientation are associated with RBV, encouraging companies to increase

organizational commitment. RBV can also increase intangible assets such as human resources; these human resources can attract, train and develop the company's innovation capabilities by increasing its organizational commitment. For this reason, this study will examine the role of organizational commitment in mediating the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME innovation performance in the DKI Jakarta area with the following hypothesis:

H₁: Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) has a positive and significant effect on Innovation Performance (IP)

H₂: Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Commitment (OC)

H₃: Organizational Commitment (OC) has a positive and significant effect on Innovation Performance (IP)

H₄: Organizational Commitment (OC) mediates the relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) and Innovation Performance (IP)

The model in this study was tested using the SmartPLS 3 application by applying a path weighting scheme. At the same time, the Bootstrapping procedure was carried out with 170 cases and 5000 subsamples [15] without changing the default settings of SmartPLS. To better understand the stages in testing the model, this article will explain the step-by-step procedure as follows:

First Step: Designing the measurement model (outer model)

The latent variable must be measured in SEM by the observed variable (indicator, item, or manifest variable). The outer model (the measurement model) determines the relationship between latent variables and their indicators. More precisely, each construct has a measurement model (outer model) that determines the relationship between each construct (circle) and its indicator variable (rectangle). In determining the measurement model for each construct, there are two choices of measurement models, namely reflective and formative. There are two different ways of measuring latent variables [4]. The first way is to connect latent constructs to indicators or commonly referred to as reflective measurements. In Fig. 1, the latent variables OC

and IP are denoted by 2 and 1 using a reflective measurement model. The second way is to link indicators to latent constructs or commonly referred to as formative measurements. In Fig. 1, the latent variable EO is denoted by 1 using a formative measurement model.

In the reflective measurement model, the latent variable is the cause of the reflective measurement indicator. The reflective measurement indicator reflects the results or observable consequences of the latent variable. In contrast, in the formative measurement model, the latent variable is understood as a consequence of the formative measurement indicator where the latent variable represents an exact linear combination or is free from measurement error [38,39,40]. The reflective indicator equation model can be written as follows:

$$x = \lambda x \xi + \delta$$

$$y = \lambda y \eta + \varepsilon$$

Where x and y are indicators for exogenous (ξ) and endogenous (η) latent variables, meanwhile, x and y are outer loadings matrices that describe simple regression coefficients that relate latent variables to their indicators. Residuals are measured by and can be interpreted as measurement error or noise. While the formative indicator equation model is written as follows:

$$x = \pi x \xi$$

$$y = \pi y \eta$$

Where x and y are indicators for exogenous (ξ) and endogenous (η) latent variables. While x and y are outer weights matrices that describe the relationship between indicator variables and latent variables.

Step Two: Designing a structural model (inner model)

After the measurement model is formed, the next step is to design a structural model (inner model). According to Hair et al. [15], the evaluation of the structural model (inner model) aims to predict the relationship between latent variables. The endogenous latent variables are identified in the structural model with the notation (η) and the exogenous latent variables with the notation (ξ). Figure 1 shows how exogenous and endogenous variables are related and can be identified with the existing notations.

Fig. 1. Notated structural model illustration

Where the notations used are:

- ξ1 = Ksi, Latent exogenous variable EO
- η1 = Eta, Latent exogenous variable OC
- η2 = Eta, Latent endogenous variable IP
- x = Manifest measurement variable of a latent exogenous variable
- y = Manifest measurement variable of a latent endogenous variable
- λx = Lambda, loading factor of exogenous latent variable
- λy = Lambda, loading factor of endogenous latent variable
- β = Beta, path coefficient of endogenous variables to endogenous variables
- γ = Gamma, path coefficient of exogenous variables to endogenous variables
- ζ = Zeta, Residual of latent endogenous variable
- δ = Delta, measurement error on manifest variable for exogenous latent variable
- ε = Epsilon, Residual of a reflective measurement variable endogenous

The structural equation above can be written as follows:

$$\eta_1 = \gamma_1 \xi_1 + \zeta_1$$

$$\eta_2 = \beta_1 \eta_1 + \gamma_2 \xi_1 + \zeta_2$$

5. PROCEDURES OF PLS-SEM MODEL EVALUATION

In evaluating the PLS-SEM model, there are two stages of testing, which have been illustrated in Fig. 2. Stage 1 tests the measurement model (outer model evaluation); the test is carried out by seeing whether the model includes a reflective measurement model (Stage 1.1), a formative measurement model (Stage 1.2), or even both. If the evaluation of the measurement model gives satisfactory results and is declared to have passed the test, the researcher can proceed to Stage 2, which involves evaluating the structural model. Stage 1 examines measurement theory, while Stage 2 includes the structural theory used to determine whether the structural relationship is significant and test hypotheses.

Fig. 2. PLS-SEM Evaluation Stage

Stage 1.1: Evaluating the Reflective Measurement Model

When the research has a reflective measurement model, the researcher can examine the loadings indicator value. When the loading value is above 0.50, it indicates that the construct can be explained by the associated indicator variance of

50%. The loadings value is obtained through the PLS Algorithm procedure in the SmartPLS application. Fig. 3 and Table 4 show the results where the loading value for each indicator has explained the latent construct above 50%. However, the minimum loadings limit will vary depending on the methodology and research objectives (see the third problem study).

Fig. 3. Test results using the PLS-algorithm procedure

The evaluation criteria for the next reflective measurement model is average variance extracted (AVE). This value is included in the convergent validity test, and the test measures the extent to which the constructs converge in the indicators by explaining the item variance. Convergent validity was assessed by average variance extracted (AVE) for all items associated with each construct. The AVE value is calculated as the average load squared for all indicators related to a construct. The acceptable AVE is 0.50 or higher, indicating that, on average, the construct explains more than 50% of the variance of the items (see Table 4).

After exceeding the testing criteria for convergent validity, the next criteria that need to be tested are problems related to discriminant validity in each construct with the correlation value between constructs in the model [41]. Wong

(2019) stated several testing steps to measure discriminant validity: the Fornell Larcker criterion, heterotrait monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT), and cross-loadings. Table 5 illustrates how the Fornell Larcker criterion test has met the test requirements, where the correlation of the square root of AVE with the target construct is higher than the square root of AVE with other constructs. As a side note, when the researcher assesses the Fornell-Larcker criterion on a model that includes a construct with a formative measurement model, the researcher only needs to compare the square root value of the AVE on the reflective construct with all the correlations of the latent variables. However, according to Hair et al. [15], the square root of the AVE of formatively measured constructs should not be compared with correlations. As shown in Table 5, the square root of AVE is not even reported for formative constructs in SmartPLS.

Table 4. Reflective measurement model test results

Measures		Loadings	Weights	Sources
Entrepreneurial Orientation (Formative Construct)				Wolff, Pett, and Ring [34]
EO_1	Being first to the market with innovative new products/services		0.102	
EO_2	Bold acts to achieve the goals		0.159	
EO_3	Exploiting risky market opportunities		0.306	
EO_4	Experimenting with new products and service		0.206	
EO_5	Initiating actions to which competitors respond		0.258	
EO_6	Proactively pursuing market opportunities		0.178	
Organizational Commitment (Refelctive Construct)				Ugaddan, Oh and Park [35]
OC_1	I feel emotionally attached to this firm	0.898		
OC_2	I feel a strong sense of belonging to my firm	0.942		
OC_3	One of the major reasons why I do not leave this firm is that I feel a sense of moral obligation to remain	0.914		
OC_4	If I got another offer for a better job elsewhere I would not feel it was right to leave my firm	0.898		
OC_5	Too much in my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my firm now	0.894		
OC_6	It would be very hard for me to leave my agency right now, even if I wanted to	0.878		
OC_7	I am afraid of what might happen if I quit my job without having another one lined up	0.874		
Innovation Performance (Refelctive Construct)				Iqbal et al. [36]
IP_1	My firm shows the willingness to support creativity	0.836		
IP_2	My firms takes the risk to venture into new unknown markets	0.902		
IP_3	My firm looks for market opportunities	0.848		

Table 5. Fornell Larcker criterion test results

	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
Entrepreneurial Orientation			
Innovation Performance	0.804	0.863	Formative
Organizational Commitment	0.881	0.763	0.900

Table 6. HTMT criterion test results

	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
Innovation Performance		
Organizational Commitment	0.854	

If referring to the opinion of Henseler et al. [31], which has been described in the previous chapter, states that the Fornell-Larcker criterion approach fails to identify discriminant validity in the majority of cases. Researchers are advised to assess discriminant validity using the heterotrait monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT). Ramayah et al. [42] explained that if the researcher found the HTMT value to be smaller than $HTMT_{0.85}$ [43] or the $HTMT_{0.90}$ value [44], as shown in Table 6, the HTMT value was found to be smaller than $HTMT_{0.85}$. It can be concluded that there is no problem with discriminant validity.

Furthermore, another alternative in testing the problem of discriminant validity is to test the $HMT_{inference}$ through a bootstrapping procedure by looking at the confidence interval value. Table 7 shows the confidence interval (CI) value, where if the value is found to be less than 1.00 at the CI (2.5%) and the CI (97.5%), it can be identified that there is no problem with discriminant validity [31].

The next stage in testing discriminant validity is to look at the value of the cross-loadings test. An indicator is declared valid if it has a higher loadings correlation between the intended constructs than the loadings correlation with other constructs (see Table 8). Thus, latent constructs predict indicators in their block better than indicators in other blocks [15].

When the researcher has confirmed the validity of the construct, the reliability test is carried out using the composite reliability test and Cronbach's alpha by looking at all values of the latent variable having a composite reliability value > 0.7 and Cronbach's alpha and ρ_a 0.6, where it can be concluded that the construct has good reliability or the questionnaire used as a tool in research have been reliable or consistent. Table 4 shows that all the internal reliability consistency values have met the requirements. As an additional note, Cronbach's alpha is the lower limit, and composite reliability is the upper limit of internal consistency reliability [15].

Table 7. $HMT_{inference}$ test results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
Entrepreneurial Orientation -> Innovation Performance	0.588	0.611	0.392	0.854
Entrepreneurial Orientation -> Organizational Commitment	0.881	0.882	0.839	0.924
Organizational Commitment -> Innovation Performance	0.245	0.224	-0.060	0.453
Entrepreneurial Orientation -> Organizational Commitment -> Innovation Performance	0.216	0.198	-0.055	0.404

Table 8. Cross-loadings test results

	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Innovation Performance	Organizational Commitment
EO_1	0.646	0.558	0.534
EO_2	0.683	0.625	0.533
EO_3	0.870	0.705	0.761
EO_4	0.892	0.714	0.789
EO_5	0.868	0.676	0.785
EO_6	0.847	0.618	0.804
IP_1	0.640	0.836	0.618
IP_2	0.727	0.902	0.696
IP_3	0.710	0.848	0.658
OC_1	0.802	0.696	0.898
OC_2	0.826	0.738	0.942
OC_3	0.802	0.704	0.914
OC_4	0.770	0.627	0.898
OC_5	0.785	0.679	0.894
OC_6	0.765	0.654	0.878
OC_7	0.795	0.702	0.874

Stage 1.2: Evaluating Formative Measurement Models

To evaluate the formative measurement model, there is a significant difference in evaluating the model on reflective measurement. Convergent validity in the formative measurement model is determined based on the extent to which the formatively measured construct correlates with the reflectively measured construct, which has the same meaning as the formatively measured construct [4]. Research conducted by Hair et al. [15] suggested that the formatively measured construct should explain at least 65% of the variance of the reflective measured item, which is indicated by a path coefficient of around 0.80. However, a path coefficient of 0.70 is also acceptable in most cases. To evaluate more specifically, researchers are advised to look at the significance of the values of the weights through the bootstrapping procedure with a suggested subsample of 5000. Using a subsample of 5000, researchers can calculate the standard bootstrapping error, which calculates the t-value (and p-value) for each indicator weight of reflective measurements.

Based on the t-value, the significance of the weight can be determined to make the following decisions (1) If the weight value is found to be statistically significant, the indicator can be maintained, (2) If the weight value is found to be insignificant, but the value of the loading is 0.50 or higher, the indicator is still allowed to be maintained, but this must be supported by theory and expert judgment, (3) If the weight value is not significant and the load is low (i.e., below 0.50), the indicator should be removed from the measurement model.

However, omitting formative indicators from the model is recommended to be avoided. This is because each indicator of the formative model represents the meaning dimension of the latent variable. Thus, eliminating indicators in the formative model is the same as eliminating the meaning dimension, causing the meaning of the latent variable to change [45]. It is unlike reflective measurement models; formative indicators are not interchangeable. Therefore, removing formative indicators has detrimental consequences on the content validity of the measurement model [46].

Table 9. Formative measurement model test results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Outer VIF
EO_1 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.102	0.100	0.058	1.760	0.049	1.670
EO_2 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.159	0.162	0.059	2.675	0.008	1.713
EO_3 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.306	0.305	0.063	4.881	0.000	2.474
EO_4 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.206	0.204	0.078	2.637	0.009	3.444
EO_5 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.258	0.259	0.080	3.242	0.001	2.915
EO_6 -> Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.178	0.176	0.074	2.409	0.016	2.737

In addition to looking at the criteria above, the evaluation of the formative measurement model is done by looking at the value of the outer VIF. To assess the level of collinearity between the formative indicators, researchers must calculate the variance inflation factor (VIF). In determining the value limit, a higher VIF implies a greater degree of collinearity between indicators. As a limit, a VIF value above five indicates collinearity between indicators (see Table 9).

Stage 2: Evaluating the Structural Model

As long as the measurement model assessment shows that the quality of the measurement model is satisfactory, the researcher can proceed to the second stage of the PLS-SEM evaluation process (Fig. 2), which is evaluating the structural model. In contrast to CB-SEM, which has several goodness-of-fit (GOF) criteria, PLS-SEM has another standard: the assessment of model quality based on its ability to predict endogenous constructions. Researchers can refer to the criteria for the coefficient of determination (R^2), cross-validated redundancy (Q^2) and model fit. However, before carrying out some of these test criteria, researchers must examine the potential for collinearity in the structural model between exogenous constructs (inner VIF). Assessing the model with PLS-SEM begins by looking at each endogenous latent variable's R-Square (R^2). R-Square (R^2) or the value of the coefficient of determination shows how much the exogenous variable explains the endogenous variable. The R-square (R^2) value is zero to one; if the value of R-Square (R^2) is getting closer to one, then the exogenous variables provide all the information needed to predict the variation of endogenous variables. The R-square (R^2) value has a weakness; for example, the value of R-Square (R^2) will increase every time there is an addition of one exogenous variable even though the exogenous variable has no significant effect on the endogenous variable.

According to Hair et al. [47,15], as a guideline, R-Squared values of 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75 represent weak, moderate, and substantial levels. However, if an R-Squared adjusted is used [15], this coefficient can be biased upward in complex models where more paths lead to endogenous constructs. Based on the illustration shown in Table 9, it was found that the IO variable could be explained by 65.6% by the exogenous variable; this was due to the finding of an R-

Square (R^2) value of 0.656. Meanwhile, the OC variable can be explained by 77.5% by the exogenous variable; this is due to the finding of an R-Square (R^2) value of 0.775.

The next criterion is to evaluate the cross-validated redundancy (Q^2) to measure how well the observed values are generated from the structural model. According to Hair et al. [15], if the Q^2 value is greater than zero for certain endogenous latent variables, the PLS-SEM path model has predictive relevance. A sample reuse technique called "Blindfolding" obtained these statistical values". The removal distance is set between 5 and 12, where the number of observations divided by the distance of removal is not an integer [48]. For example, if applied researchers select an omission distance of 7, every seventh data point is omitted, and the parameter is estimated with the remaining data points. According to Hair et al. [15], the omitted data points are considered missing values replaced with average values. The estimated parameters help predict the omitted data points and the difference between the actual data points and the predicted data points becomes the input for the Q^2 calculation. Blindfolding is only applied to endogenous constructions with reflective indicators. If Q^2 is greater than zero, it shows the value of predictive relevance to the path model in endogenous construction and the corresponding reflective indicators.

Applied researchers must be careful in reporting and using model fit criteria in PLS-SEM [15]. This is not without reason; the criteria are still in the early stages of research and have not been fully approved by statistical methodologists (e.g., threshold values). However, some researchers have started to report the fit model in the PLS-SEM method. SmartPLS has provided several model fit criteria, but these values still need to be reviewed repeatedly to be applied properly. In several previous studies, these criteria were not reported or used to assess PLS-SEM results [15]. Hair et al. [15] suggest that researchers use SRMR, RMS_{theta} , or Exact Fit values. However, due to the absence of in-depth research on these three criteria, researchers are advised to follow a conservative approach. If the SRMR value is less than 0.08 and the RMS_{theta} value is less than 0.12, the fit model can be accepted. Of note, Hair et al. [15] forbid using the GOF criteria (proposed by Tenenhaus et al., [24]) to evaluate this test (see the previous section on the study of problem findings).

Table 10. Predictive relevance test results

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Entrepreneurial Orientation	1020.000	1020.000			
Innovation Performance	510.000	265.564	0.479	0.660	0.656
Organizational Commitment	1190.000	450.835	0.621	0.776	0.775

6. HYPOTHESES TESTING

This stage examines how the exogenous latent variable is connected with the endogenous latent variable. To test the hypothesis that has been proposed, researchers can see the path coefficient value, T-Statistic value and p-value through the bootstrapping procedure. In carrying out the bootstrapping procedure, Hair et al. [15] confirmed that researchers should use the Bias-Corrected and Accelerated (BCa) Bootstrap method to assess the significance of the path coefficients in the structural model. Alternatively, the researcher can return to the p-value (<0.05).

Hair et al. [46] explain that the path coefficient value is always -1 to +1. The path coefficient value approaching +1 represents a strong positive relationship, and the path coefficient value of -1 indicates a strong negative relationship. Based on the path coefficient test in Fig. 4 and Table 11, it can be seen that all relationships have a positive relationship direction because the value is close to +1. Furthermore, the researcher can see the T-Statistic value to see the significant value between constructs. The limit for rejecting and accepting the proposed hypothesis is ±1.96, which if the t-statistic value is below 1.96, then the hypothesis will be rejected.

Fig. 4. Bootstrapping procedure test results

Table 11. Research hypothesis testing results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Direct					
EO -> IP	0.588	0.611	0.114	5.160	0.000
EO -> OC	0.881	0.882	0.022	39.628	0.000
OC -> IP	0.245	0.224	0.121	2.026	0.043
Indirect					
EO -> OC -> IP	0.216	0.198	0.107	2.017	0.044

Notes:

- 'a' : exogenous variable on mediator variable
- 'b' : mediator variable on endogenous variable
- 'c' : exogenous variable on endogenous variable

Fig. 5. Mediation role decision tree

Based on the test results, it can be seen that all hypotheses in this study are accepted; this is due to the finding of p-values below than 0.05. EO was found to be directly increase IP in a positive ($\beta=0.588$) and significant ($t=5.160$) direction. Therefore, the higher an individual's entrepreneurial orientation, the higher their innovation performance. The next finding is that there is an influence between EO on OC with a positive direction ($\beta=0.881$) and significant ($t=39.628$); it can be concluded that the higher the entrepreneurial orientation possessed by individuals, the higher their organizational commitment will be. In the subsequent direct hypothesis testing, it was found that there was an influence of OC on IP with a positive direction ($\beta=0.245$) and significant ($t=2.026$); it can be concluded that the higher the organizational

commitment of individuals, the higher their innovation performance.

7. ASSESSING THE MEDIATING EFFECT

The mediating effect is used to see the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables through connecting variables. The effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables does not occur directly but through a transformation process represented by mediating variables [49]. Testing the mediation effect can be done using regression techniques, but the regression technique is no longer efficient in complex models or with many paths leading to endogenous constructs. The Variance Accounted For (VAF) method developed by Preacher & Hayes, [50] and bootstrapping in the distribution

of indirect effects is considered more suitable because it does not require any assumptions about the distribution of variables applied to small sample sizes.

However, the VAF method can only be carried out by considering several conditions such as (1) the direct effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables must be significant, (2) each path, namely exogenous variables on mediating variables and mediating variables on endogenous variables must be significant to fulfil this condition [51,52]. Suppose the two conditions above have been obtained. In that case, the researcher can use the VAF formula, namely the effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable multiplied by the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable [46]. If the indirect effect is significant, then this indicates that the mediating variable can absorb or reduce the direct effect in the first test. Here is the VAF formula:

$$\text{VAF} = \frac{\text{indirect effect}}{\text{total effect}} \dots\dots \text{Sarstedt et al. [4]}$$

When the researcher found the VAF value above 80%, then the value indicated the full mediation role. Categorized as partial mediation if the VAF value ranges from 20% to 80%, but if the VAF value is less than 20%, it can be concluded that there is almost no mediating effect.

However, in a later study, Hair et al. [15] revised the method above by suggesting not to look at the VAF value anymore but suggesting to look at the changes in the existing effects (see Fig. 5) from a direct to an indirect relationship with the following conditions (1) Direct-only nonmediation, the condition is found if the effect is a significant direct effect, but not with indirect effect; (2) No-effect non-mediation, a condition where the direct or indirect effects are found to be insignificant; (3) Complementary mediation, this condition is found when the indirect effect and direct effect are found to be significant and point in the same direction; (4) Competitive mediation, a condition where indirect and direct effects are found to be significant but have opposite directions; (5) Indirect-only mediation, is a condition where the indirect effect is significant but not with a direct effect. Table 11 illustrates how the mediating variable, namely OC, was found to have a complementary mediation mediating role, this is because the direct relationship (EO→IP) and indirect (EO→OC→IP) effects were found to have a significant effect ($t=2.017$) and point in the same direction ($\beta=0.216$).

8. CONCLUSION

The decision to use the CB-SEM or PLS-SEM methods is not based on which method is better. If researchers want to go back to the basics of developing statistical methodologies, they will understand the “how” and “what” each method was developed for. In addition, the decision to use it is also not based on one assumption and does not seem to see other assumptions; for example, applied researchers often decide to use PLS-SEM because of the small sample size, but rarely from researchers who consider the minimum value limit (such as loadings) required to cover the sample shortage. When a researcher decides to use SEM-PLS with an example of these reasons, the researcher will also be faced with fulfilling other assumption criteria that can cover the existing deficiencies. Another common reason for choosing is that PLS-SEM is perceived as the method of choice when researchers are faced with data that are not normally distributed. However, researchers still insist on testing the empirical model using excessive goodness-of-fit criteria. On the other hand, statistical methodologists are still trying to establish model fit criteria for PLS-SEM.

Researchers should be able to make wise decisions by considering all the situations and conditions they face. In short, both CB-SEM and PLS-SEM have different parameters and rules of use estimates. Therefore, applied researchers should consider many assumptions when deciding to apply PLS-SEM in their research; for example, if the research conducted is confirmatory, researchers are advised to use the CB-SEM method. The author hopes that this article can help applied researchers decide which methods to apply to the quantitative research they are running and provide a clear picture of the procedures and stages of using the PLS-SEM method.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Dijkstra TK. Latent variables and indices: Herman world's basic design and partial least squares. In V. Esposito Vinzi, W. W. Chin, J. Henseler, H. Wang (Eds.), Handbook of partial least squares: Concepts, methods and applications

- (Springer Handbooks of Computational Statistics Series). Heidelberg/Dordrecht/London/New York: Springer. 2010;II:23-46.
2. Jöreskog KG, Wold HOA. The ML and PLS techniques for modeling with latent variables: Historical and comparative aspects. In H. O. A. Wold & K. G. Jöreskog (Eds.), *Systems under indirect observation, part I* (pp. 263–270). Amsterdam: North-Holland; 1982.
 3. Rigdon EE. Rethinking partial least squares path modeling: In praise of simple methods. *Long Range Planning*. 2012; 45(5–6):341–358.
 4. Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Smith D, Reams R, Hair JF. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): A useful tool for family business researchers. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*. 2014; 5(1):105–115.
 5. Antonakis J, Bendahan S, Jacquart P, Lalive R. On making causal claims: A review and recommendations. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 2010;21(6):1086-1120. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2010.10.010>
 6. Vandenberg RJ. Introduction: Statistical and methodological myths and urban legends: Where, pray tell, did they get this idea? *Organizational Research Methods*. 2006;9(2):194-201. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428105285506>
 7. Rönkkö M, McIntosh CN, Antonakis J, Edwards JR. Partial least squares path modeling: Time for some serious second thoughts. *Journal of Operations Management*. 2016;47:9-27. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2016.05.002>
 8. Aguirre-Urreta MI, Marakas GM. A rejoinder to rigdon et al (2014). *Information Systems Research*. 2014;25(4):785-788. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2014.0545>
 9. McIntosh CN, Edwards JR, Antonakis J. Reflections on partial least squares path modeling. *Organizational Research Methods*. 2014;17(2):210-251. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428114529165>
 10. Goodhue DL, Lewis W, Thompson R. Comparing PLS to regression and LISREL: A response to Marcoulides, Chin and Saunders. *Mis Quarterly*. 2012;703-716. Available:<https://doi.org/10.2307/41703476>
 11. Aguirre-Urreta MI, Rönkkö M. Statistical inference with PLS using bootstrap confidence intervals. *MIS Quarterly*, 2018;42(3):1001-1020. Available:<https://doi.org/10.25300/misq/2018/13587>
 12. Afthanorhan A, Awang Z, Aimran N. Five common mistakes for using partial least squares path modeling (PLS-PM) in management research. *Contemporary Management Research*. 2020;16(4):255–278.
 13. Lohmöller JB. Predictive vs. structural modeling: PLS vs. ML. In *Latent Variable Path Modeling with Partial Least Squares* (pp. 199-226). Physica, Heidelberg; 1989. Available:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-52512-4_5
 14. Henseler J, Hubona G, Ray PA. Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: Updated guidelines. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*. 2016;116(1):2-20. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1108/imds-09-2015-0382>
 15. Hair Jr. JF, Matthews LM, Matthews RL, Sarstedt M. PLS-SEM or CB-SEM: Updated guidelines on which method to use. *International Journal of Multivariate Data Analysis*. 2017;1(2):107-123. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmda.2017.087624>
 16. Ringle CM, Sarstedt M, Mitchell R, Gudergan SP. Partial least squares structural equation modeling in HRM research. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 2018;1-27.
 17. Sarstedt M, Hair JF, Ringle CM, Thiele KO, Gudergan SP. Estimation issues with PLS and CBSEM: Where the bias lies!. *Journal of Business Research*. 2016;69(10):3998-4010. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.06.00>
 18. Schuberth F, Henseler J, Dijkstra TK. Partial least squares path modeling using ordinal categorical indicators. *Quality & Quantity*. 2018;52(1):9-35. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-016-0401-7>
 19. Hwang H, Takane Y, Tenenhaus A. An alternative estimation procedure for partial least squares path modeling. *Behavior-metrika*. 2015;42(1):63-78. Available:<https://doi.org/10.2333/bhmk.42.63>

20. Rönkkö M, McIntosh CN, Antonakis J. On the adoption of partial least squares in psychological research: Caveat emptor. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 2015;87:76-84. Available:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.07.019
21. Ioannidis JP. Why most published research findings are false. *PLoS Medicine*. 2005; 2(8):e124.
22. Wagenmakers EJ, Wetzels R, Borsboom D, van der Maas HL, Kievit RA. An agenda for purely confirmatory research. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 2012;7(6):632-638. Available:https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612463078
23. Henseler J. Bridging design and behavioral research with variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of Advertising*. 2017;46(1):178-192. Available:https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2017.1281780
24. Tenenhaus M, Amato S, Esposito VV. A global goodness-of-fit index for PLS structural equation modeling. In *Proceedings of the XLII SIS Scientific Meeting*. Padova, Italy: CLEUP. 2004;739–742.
25. Tenenhaus M, Esposito Vinzi V, Chatelin YM, Lauro C. PLS path modeling. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2005;48:159–205.
26. Henseler J, Sarstedt M. Goodness-of-fit indices for partial least squares path modeling. *Computational Statistics*. 2013; 28:565–580.
27. Henseler J, Dijkstra TK, Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Diamantopoulos A, Straub DW, et al. Common beliefs and reality about partial least squares: Comments on Rönkkö & Evermann (2013). *Organizational Research Methods*. 2014;17:182–209.
28. Hu LT, Bentler PM. Fit indices in covariance structure modeling: Sensitivity to under parameterized model misspecification. *Psychological Methods*. 1998;3: 424–453.
29. Dijkstra TK, Henseler J. Consistent partial least squares path modeling. *MIS Quarterly*. 2015b;39:297–316.
30. Dijkstra TK, Henseler J. Consistent and asymptotically normal PLS estimators for linear structural equations. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2015a;81:10–23.
31. Henseler J, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 2015;43(1):115-135. Available:https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8
32. Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Hair JF. Partial least squares structural equation modeling with R. *Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation*. 2017;21:2017.
33. Polkinghorne DE. Language and meaning: Data collection in qualitative research. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*. 2005; 52(2):137-145. Available:https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.52.2.137
34. James A. Wolff, Timothy L. Pett, J. Kirk Ring. Small firm growth as a function of both learning orientation and entrepreneurial orientation. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*. 2015;21(5):709–730.
35. Ugaddan R, Oh HG, Park SM. An exploration of entrepreneurial orientation and organizational commitment: A focus on the role of public service motivation. *Asian Rev. Public Adm.* 2016;27:4–24.
36. Iqbal S, Moleiro Martins J, Nuno Mata M, Naz S, Akhtar S, Abreu A. Linking entrepreneurial orientation with innovation performance in SMES; the role of organizational commitment and transformational leadership using smart PLS-SEM. *Sustainability*. 2021;13(8):4361. MDPI AG. Available:http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13084361
37. Kee D, Rahman NA. Entrepreneurial orientation, innovation and SME performance: A study of SMEs in Malaysia using PLS-SEM. *GATR Global Journal of Business Social Sciences Review*. 2020;8: 73-80. DOI: 10.35609/gjbssr.2020.8.2(1)
38. Fornell CG, Bookstein FL. Two structural equation models: LISREL and PLS applied to consumer exit-voice theory. *Journal of Marketing Research*. 1982;19(4):440–452.
39. Edwards JR, Bagozzi RP. On the nature and direction of relationships between constructs and measures. *Psychological Methods*. 2000;5(2):155–174.
40. Diamantopoulos A. Incorporating formative measures into covariance-based structural equation models. *MIS Quarterly*. 2011; 35(2):335–358.
41. Wong KK. Mediation analysis, categorical moderation analysis, and higher-order

- constructs modeling in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM): A B2B Example using SmartPLS, Marketing Bulletin, 26, Technical Note 1. 2016;1-22.
42. Ramayah T, Cheah J, Chuah F, Ting H, Memon MA. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 3.0: An updated and practical guide to statistical analysis. Singapore: Pearson; 2016.
 43. Kline RB. Principles and practice of structural equation modeling. Guilford publications; 2015.
 44. Gold AH, Malhotra A, Segars AH. Knowledge management: An organizational capabilities perspective. Journal of Management Information Systems. 2001; 18(1):185–214. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2001.11045669>
 45. Garson GD. Partial least squares regression and structural equation models. Asheboro: Statistical Associates; 2016.
 46. Hair JF, Jr., Hult GTM, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. A primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications Ltd; 2014.
 47. Hair JF, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice. 2011;19(2):139–151.
 48. Hair JF, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. Partial least squares: The better approach to structural equation modeling? Long Range Planning. 2012;45(5–6):312–319.
 49. Baron RM, Kenny DA. The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic and statistical considerations. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology. 1986;51:1173–1182.
 50. Preacher KJ, Hayes AF. Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in simple and multiple mediator models. Behavior Research Methods. 2008a;40: 879–891.
 51. Hair JF, Sarstedt M, Pieper T, Ringle CM. The use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in strategic management research: A review of past practices and recommendations for future applications. Long Range Planning. 2012;45:320–340.
 52. Hair JF, Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Mena JA. An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. 2012;40: 414–433.

© 2022 Putra; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<https://www.sdiarticle5.com/review-history/86493>

Permasalahan, Kepercayaan Umum dan Prosedur Penggunaan Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling Pada Penelitian Bisnis

Partial least squares structural equation modeling atau biasa disebut sebagai PLS-SEM dikembangkan bukan tanpa alasan. PLS-SEM dikembangkan sebagai alternatif untuk covariance-based SEM, yang memungkinkan peneliti untuk menjalankan penelitian exploratory. Selain itu, PLS-SEM dinilai mampu memberikan fleksibilitas terkait dengan karakteristik data, kompleksitas model maupun model spesifikasi. Tak ayal, PLS-SEM menjadi metode paling sering digunakan dalam banyak bidang di penelitian bisnis. Namun demikian, banyak dari peneliti yang menggunakan PLS-SEM secara tidak tepat bahkan berekspektasi lebih tanpa memahami dasar metode structural equation modeling. Untuk itu, artikel ini akan membahas mengenai berbagai jenis permasalahan dan kepercayaan umum atas penggunaan PLS-SEM dalam penelitian bisnis. Selain itu, artikel ini dapat dijadikan referensi untuk memudahkan peneliti terapan memutuskan metode, teknik dan alat seperti apa yang akan digunakan untuk menyelesaikan penelitiannya. Sebagai tambahan, pada bagian akhir artikel ini akan membahas mengenai bagaimana PLS-SEM dapat diterapkan untuk mengembangkan teori dalam penelitian bisnis melalui serangkaian pengantar teknis dengan mempertimbangkan kebutuhan pengguna. Artikel ini dilengkapi dengan prosedur sistematis yang membahas alur evaluasi setiap pengujian PLS-SEM melalui ilustrasi dengan model bernotasi menggunakan SmartPLS.

Wawas Bangun Tegar Sunaryo Putra merupakan Founder yang sekaligus menjabat sebagai Chief Executive Officer untuk Indonesian School of Research by WRC Group. Wawas Bangun juga aktif sebagai peneliti yang secara rutin mempublikasikan artikel penelitian ilmiah dan buku, khususnya di bidang SEM-PLS. Ia telah banyak diundang untuk berbicara pada forum akademis di berbagai Universitas untuk menyampaikan materi metodologi penelitian dan statistik. Semangatnya adalah untuk mengajarkan orang-orang dari seluruh latar belakang industri maupun pendidikan agar mampu mengerti dan memahami bagaimana melakukan penelitian yang baik dan benar. Tidak hanya itu, Wawas Bangun telah sukses

meluncurkan berbagai jenis pelatihan melalui produk Indonesian School of Research yaitu Research Bootcamp Private Class, Research Bootcamp Group Class, serta webinar bertajuk "Virtual Webinar on Applied Structural Equation Modeling (VWASEM)" sejak tahun 2020. Wawas Bangun juga aktif sebagai Educational Youtuber yang berfokus pada konten edukasi penelitian yang telah berhasil mendapatkan perhatian dengan jumlah penonton terbanyak untuk video tutorial SEM-PLS.